

Parametric Coupling to Low Frequency Plasma Waves

by

Charles Fielding Finch Karney

B.A., Cambridge University

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Thesis Supervisor: Abraham Bers
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Department of Electrical Engineering, January 28, 1974

Certified by

Thesis Supervisor

Accepted by

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NOTATION

Note: Scalar quantities are represented by italics (m , q , etc.); vector by Roman serif (E , r , etc.) and tensors by bold roman (I , σ , etc.).

We adopt the convention in which field quantities vary as $\exp[ik \cdot r - i\omega t]$.

References occurring in the text are put in square brackets, thus: [Pa1].

In this list below the numbers occurring in parentheses refer to equation numbers in the text.

Normal variables (those conforming with usual notation have been omitted)

a, b, n	the interacting modes (pump, idler and signal)
γ_n	damping rate of mode n
θ	the angle between k and B_0
ξ, ζ	$\sin \theta, \cos \theta$ (3.1.9)
μ	mass ratio m_i/m_e
s	species, either e (electron) or i (ion)
D	electromagnetic dispersion tensor (2.1.9)
I	the identity tensor
σ	linear conductivity (2.1.3)
E_0	unperturbed mode amplitude (2.1.12)
W_0	energy density of unperturbed mode (2.1.13)
v_σ	group velocity (2.1.14)
c_s	ion acoustic speed (3.2.18)
v_{ts}	thermal velocity of species s (2.4.11)
ω_p	plasma frequency (2.4.26)
Ω	cyclotron frequency (2.4.34)
Δ	(2.4.27)
Λ	(2.4.28-33)
J_{ext}	external driving current (2.2.2)
u	perturbed mode amplitude, normalized to unity (2.2.3)
$J_{m,p}^{(2)}$	second order current produced by modes m and p (2.3.5)
$\delta k, \delta \omega$	wave vector and frequency mismatch (2.3.11-12)
K	(2.3.8)
M	coupling coefficient for the nonlinear interaction (2.3.14)
γ_0	growth rate in the absence of damping (2.3.20)
R	driving term to second order continuity equation (2.4.15 and 41)
P	driving term to second order momentum equation (2.4.16 and 42)
J_c	flowcurrent (2.4.43)
K	dielectric tensor (3.1.5)
K	electostatic dispersion relation (3.1.6)
R_s	(3.1.11)
Q	(3.1.13)
α, β	see figure 3.4.2(a)
ψ	see figure 3.4.4(a)
δ	expansion parameter (4.3.13)
ϵ_1, ϵ_2 etc	small parameters

λ_1, λ_2 etc	(4.3.14-15)
C	(4.3.24)
n_0'	density gradient
x_0	position of lower hybrid resonance layer
x'	x/x_0

MACSYMA variables

WN	ω/Ω_i
KN	$[KNX,KNY,KNZ] = k c_s/\Omega_i$
KNM	$k c_s/\Omega_i$
A, B, N	a, b, n ; WN[A] means WN for mode A
SIGMAN	$s \Omega_i / (i \epsilon_0 \omega_{pi}^2)$
VI	SIGMAN.KN
VIT	KN.SIGMAN
NI	KN.(VI/WN)
MU	μ
GM2	$\gamma - 2$
M	M/C
MION, MIFLOW etc	various terms in M
DTA	δ
LM1, LM2 etc	λ_1, λ_2 etc
ALP, BET	α, β
CONVEC, TERM1 etc	dummy variables for tracing nonlinear terms

CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1 *Motivation*

The focus of plasma physics research over the past decade has been the attainment of controlled thermo-nuclear fusion. The goal is simply enough stated as being the confinement of a hot dense plasma for long enough for a significant number of its ions to fuse, with a resultant release of energy.

Lately much attention has been given to a class of magnetic confinement devices, known as *tokamaks* [Ar1]. In these toroidal devices confinement is by an externally applied toroidal field, acting together with a pinching poloidal field, that is produced by a toroidal current in the plasma. This stabilizing current also serves to heat the plasma by ordinary Ohmic resistance. Indications are that present day machines can be scaled up in size, so that the conditions on density and confinement time are met. However there may be an upper limit on the ion temperature that can be achieved with Ohmic heating alone. This is because classical Ohmic resistance is a decreasing function of electron temperature, and so Ohmic heating becomes ineffective when the ions are still below the so-called ignition temperature. (An additional deficiency of Ohmic heating is that it preferentially heats the electrons; however the confinement times of tokamaks are generally large enough that the ion and electron temperatures are approximately equilibrated.)

To increase the ion temperature we require some method by which additional energy can be given the ions. One possible scheme would be to excite low frequency plasma waves in which the ion motion is dominant [St1]. If these waves can be

driven with sufficient amplitude, heating of the ions can take place, either by ion Landau damping or by particle trapping. The waves in this class, that we consider here, are the ion acoustic, electrostatic ion cyclotron and magnetosonic waves. However a finite plasma is a near perfect reflector of waves at such low frequencies; and we cannot contemplate the introduction of grids into the plasma. One promising solution to this dilemma is to introduce high frequency plasma waves, which can be excited externally. If these are of sufficient amplitude they can act as the pump of a parametric interaction resulting in the excitation of the low frequency waves.

From the Manley - Rowe relations (equation 2.3.13), we find that the parametric conversion of energy to low frequencies is most efficient if the pump frequency is as close as possible to that of the excited waves. The best candidates for the pump then appear to be electrostatic waves near the lower hybrid resonance (we shall call these waves simply *lower hybrid waves*), or hydromagnetic waves near the ion cyclotron frequency. These are the lowest frequency modes that can be directly excited in a plasma [St2, St3]. We consider in this thesis the parametric excitation of ion acoustic, electrostatic ion cyclotron and magnetosonic waves by such a pump near the lower hybrid frequency.

There is an additional, and entirely separate reason for interest in the work reported here: the analytic expressions for the growth rates of the excited waves were obtained using a computer based symbolic manipulator, MACSYMA, that is being developed by the Matlab group of project MAC, M.I.T. (see the references given in section 4.1). Most people prefer working with a simple analytic expression as opposed to a mass of numbers that a conventional computer system might produce. The task facing us in using MACSYMA was the reduction of large complex expressions

to expressions small enough to be readily appreciated. That we were in some measure successful must be regarded as a reason for a thorough examination of the role of symbolic computation as an aid to the physicist.

1.2 *History of the Problem*

The heating of a plasma by incident radio frequency radiation near the lower hybrid frequency was first proposed by Stix [St3], who showed that in cold plasma theory, the lower hybrid resonance was accessible to an exterior source. His work has been extended by Briggs and Parker [Br1], who give details of how energy from a waveguide penetrates into an inhomogeneous plasma. A brief description of their work is given in section 5.1. Direct observation of lower hybrid waves in a laboratory plasma has recently been made by Hooke and Bernabei [Ho1].

The nonlinear theory we will use in this work treats the *coherent* interactions of several waves. There are two principle approaches to such a problem. The *oscillating frame* approach treats one wave, the *pump*, as being large enough to cause zero order perturbations in the plasma. The theory has been successfully applied to plasma problems by Nishikawa [Ni1] and Porkolab [Po1], among others. Work in which the pump has been taken to be a lower hybrid wave has been done by Kindel et al. [Ki1] and Widing [Wi1]. One drawback of this formalism is that it appears to be possible to apply it only in cases where the pump has no spatial variation ($k = 0$). (One of the interactions we consider - coupling to two ion acoustic waves - depends on there being a non-zero pump wave number.)

The other description of coherent nonlinear wave phenomena makes use of the coupling of modes formalism. This formalism, which was first developed for parametric electronics (see for example in reference Lo1), has been extended to

parametric interactions in a plasma by several workers [Sj1, Sj2, Po2, Et1, Ha1, Wi2]. In order to carry their analysis as far as possible, they have generally made simplifying assumptions about the plasma or about the geometry of the interaction. Although we do make some assumptions about the waves and the plasma in the work described here (see section 1.3), we do not make any assumptions about the geometry of the interactions. The approach we adopt here follows that of Bers [Be1]. Watson and Bers [Wa1] have recently extended the nonlinear coupling of modes formalism, and shown that it can give all the results of oscillating frame theory, and can include the effects of the pump having a finite wavenumber.

Experimental observation of parametric coupling from lower hybrid waves has been made by Hooke and Bernabei [Ho2], and by Chu et al. [Ch1]. A heating experiment which involves the excitation of lower hybrid waves is planned for ALCATOR [Pa1].

Kulp [Ku2] gives a survey of the field of symbolic computation as it applies to the field of plasma physics.

1.3 *Summary of Following Chapters*

We consider in this thesis a low β plasma such that $\Omega_e^2 \gg \omega_{pe}^2$ and $\omega_{pi} \gg \Omega_i$. Such a plasma is typical of many tokamaks. The calculations of coupling coefficients for the nonlinear interaction are made assuming that the plasma is *homogeneous*, that the magnetic field is uniform and that there is no d.c. drift of either species. Since we are dealing with the nonlinear interactions of coherent plasma waves, and since the waves we consider (see section 3.3) are all fluid modes describable in the electrostatic approximation, we will describe our plasma using the "two fluid" equations, and Maxwell's equations in the electrostatic limit (see

section 3.1). Note that we cannot examine the excitation of non-fluid modes (like the ion cyclotron bands) within this model. The two fluid equations may be derived from the Vlasov equation [Kr1] for the distribution function, $f(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{v}, t)$, for each species (electrons and ions):

$$[\partial/\partial t + \mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla_{\mathbf{r}} + \mathbf{a} \cdot \nabla_{\mathbf{v}}] f(\mathbf{r}, \mathbf{v}, t) = 0 \quad (1)$$

where:

$$\mathbf{a} = q (\mathbf{E} + \mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B})/m \quad (2)$$

and where $\nabla_{\mathbf{r}}$ and $\nabla_{\mathbf{v}}$ are the gradient operators in real and velocity space respectively. By multiplying (1) by powers of \mathbf{v} and integrating over velocity space we obtain the well know set of "moment equations" [Kr1], the first two members of which are:

$$\partial n/\partial t + \nabla \cdot (n \mathbf{v}) = 0 \quad (3)$$

$$m n (\partial/\partial t + \mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v} + \nabla p = n q (\mathbf{E} + \mathbf{v} \times \mathbf{B}) \quad (4)$$

Now all the quantities appearing here have been averaged over velocity space. These moment equations can be interpreted as statements of conservation of particles and momentum, in which each species of the plasma is regarded as being a separate fluid. The moment equations form an infinite set of equations, which cannot be closed. Closure is usually made using physical reasoning. The most commonly adopted one is to express the pressure p in terms of the density n using an equation of state of the form:

$$p = n_0 \kappa T (n/n_0)^\gamma \quad (5)$$

Here T , the temperature, is taken to be constant for the electron or ion fluid. γ is a constant, which is found to be a function only of the wave number and frequency of a disturbance (and of course of the species) whose value must be found either by physical arguments or from the solutions of the Vlasov equations. (Only in certain cases can it be identified with a "ratio of specific heats", in analogy with a

perfect gas.) The one additional assumption we will make in this work is that the ion temperature T_i is zero. This does not materially affect the dispersion relations of the waves we consider, although it will change their damping rates. When we consider the thresholds of the interactions (sec 4.6) we will take damping rates from kinetic theory, including finite ion temperature.

In chapter 2, we review the coupling of modes formalism that is used in the following chapters. Section 2.1 describes a general unperturbed system; in section 2.2 we examine the effect of perturbing Maxwell's equations with an external current, J_{ext} . In section 2.3 we apply the formalism to nonlinear wave - wave interactions, and identify J_{ext} with a second order nonlinear current $J^{(2)}$ that is produced when more than one mode exists in a nonlinear medium. Finally in section 2.4 we evaluate $J^{(2)}$ for the plasma model discussed above.

Chapter 3 describes the linear waves we consider. In section 3.1 we derive the electrostatic dispersion relation for our two fluid plasma; and in section 3.2 we show how this gives simple dispersion relations for the waves in various limits. The physical characteristics of the waves are discussed in section 3.3. In section 3.4 we examine the "resonance conditions". These determine which waves will interact strongest in a nonlinear medium.

In chapter 4 we calculate the growth rates of the excited waves. Since extensive use was made of MACSYMA for this work, section 4.1 describes some of the features of MACSYMA. In section 4.2 we describe the use of MACSYMA in obtaining numerical results for the coupling coefficients. Sections 4.3 and 4.4 describe their derivation, *analytically*, for the two principle classes of interactions considered. In section 4.5 we discuss the results of the previous two sections; and in section 4.6 we take the expressions for the coupling coefficients, and use

them to calculate growth rates of the waves and thresholds for the interactions.

All the work up to this point has been on a homogeneous plasma. In chapter 5 we apply our results to an inhomogeneous plasma. Section 5.1 describes the linear theory of propagation in an inhomogeneous plasma as developed by Briggs and Parker [Br1]. Section 5.2 considers the circumstances under which significant energy transfer to the low frequency modes is possible.

CHAPTER TWO
COUPLING OF MODES

2.1 The Unperturbed System

Coupling of modes theory was developed a number of years ago to describe how a circuit acts when weakly coupled to another. The idea was that so long as the coupling was weak enough, to a first approximation the circuits would each act as they would in the absence of the other. The effect of the coupling then would be to slowly modulate the currents in each circuit. The theory has been extended to continuous systems. In this case the effect of the coupling is to slowly modulate the natural modes of the system. Since the theory is one in which some system is only weakly perturbed, it is necessary to first understand the unperturbed state of the system before the coupled state can be analyzed. For this reason we will devote this section to the study of the unperturbed system.

The starting point for the theory for continuous systems is Maxwell's equations:

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{E} + \mu_0 \partial \mathbf{H} / \partial t = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{H} - \epsilon_0 \partial \mathbf{E} / \partial t = \mathbf{J} \quad (2)$$

Clearly the only place where the material properties of the medium enter these equations is in the current \mathbf{J} . For *linear time and space independent systems* the most general form for \mathbf{J} is [Be1]:

$$\mathbf{J}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\mathbf{r}' \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dt' \boldsymbol{\sigma}(\mathbf{r}', t') \cdot \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}', t - t') \quad (3)$$

This convolution in real space and time becomes a product in wave vector and frequency space. We define a Fourier - Laplace transform:

$$\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{k}, \omega) \equiv \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} d\mathbf{r} \int_{-\infty}^{\infty} dt \mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}, t) \exp(-i\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{r} + i\omega t) \quad (4)$$

the real electric field may be recovered by inverse transforming:

$$E(\mathbf{r}, t) = \int_{\mathcal{C}} d\mathbf{k} / (2\pi)^3 \int_{\mathcal{C}} d\omega / 2\pi E(\mathbf{k}, \omega) \exp(i\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{r} - i\omega t) \quad (5)$$

where \mathcal{C} is a contour in the complex ω plane passing above all the singularities of $E(\mathbf{k}, \omega)$. Note that $E(\mathbf{r}, t)$ and $E(\mathbf{k}, \omega)$ are *not* the same function. They are distinguished by their arguments. Later on we will omit these arguments and rely on the context to determine whether a quantity is transformed or not. Transforming all quantities in this way equation 3 becomes:

$$J(\mathbf{k}, \omega) = \boldsymbol{\sigma}(\mathbf{k}, \omega) \cdot E(\mathbf{k}, \omega) \quad (6)$$

and equations 1 and 2 become:

$$i\mathbf{k} \times E(\mathbf{k}, \omega) - \mu_0 i\omega H(\mathbf{k}, \omega) = 0 \quad (7)$$

$$i\mathbf{k} \times H(\mathbf{k}, \omega) + \epsilon_0 i\omega E(\mathbf{k}, \omega) = J(\mathbf{k}, \omega) \quad (8)$$

Eliminating J and H from these equations we obtain:

$$\mathbf{D}(\mathbf{k}, \omega) \cdot E \equiv [\mathbf{k}\mathbf{k} - k^2 \mathbf{I} + \omega^2 \epsilon_0 \mu_0 \mathbf{K}] \cdot E = 0 \quad (9)$$

where we have introduced the dielectric tensor:

$$\mathbf{K} \equiv \mathbf{I} + i\boldsymbol{\sigma} / \omega \epsilon_0 \quad (10)$$

Then the condition that $E \neq 0$ yields the linear dispersion relation:

$$D(\mathbf{k}, \omega) \equiv \det[\mathbf{D}(\mathbf{k}, \omega)] = 0 \quad (11)$$

What we have derived here is the complete electromagnetic dispersion relation. As we see it is a relation between the allowed frequencies and wave vectors of the system, in the absence of any external driving forces. A set of fields with (\mathbf{k}, ω) satisfying (11) is usually called a *natural* or *normal* mode of the system. For many purposes (11) is unnecessarily complicated. The waves of interest to us are adequately described by the quasi electrostatic approximation. This limit is discussed in section 3.1.

There are two quantities associated with the linear modes that we shall use later. They are the average energy density (\overline{W}) of the mode and its group velocity

or velocity of energy propagation (v_g). It is only possible to rigorously define these quantities if the medium is lossless, i.e. if the waves are undamped. If we take the electric field of a mode to be:

$$E(r, t) = \text{Re} [E_0 \exp(ik \cdot r - i\omega t)] \quad (12)$$

(we use the subscript 0 to indicate that the mode is unperturbed) then:

$$W_0 = \frac{1}{4}\mu_0 |H_0|^2 + \frac{1}{4}\epsilon_0 E_0^* \cdot \partial(\omega \mathbf{K})/\partial\omega \cdot E_0 \quad (13)$$

$$v_g = \partial\omega/\partial k \quad (14)$$

Bers gives a derivation of these results [Be1]. He also shows that it is possible to extend the definitions of energy density and group velocity to cover weakly damped modes (i.e. $\gamma \equiv \text{Im}(\omega) \ll \text{Re}(\omega)$ for real k). Writing the conductivity σ as $\sigma_h + i\sigma_a$ (the hermitian and anti-hermitian components), the loss mechanism in an electric system is traceable to σ_h (this part acts like a resistance). Then if:

$$|\sigma_{hij}| \ll |\sigma_{aij}| \quad (15)$$

it is possible to regard σ_h as perturbing a lossless system (with $\sigma = i\sigma_a$), in which the modes are given (for real k) by $\omega = \omega_r$. The forms of W and v_g (equations 13 and 14) remain the same, with \mathbf{K}_h replacing \mathbf{K} , and with the differentials evaluated at ω_r . (Note that now E_0 will be a slowly varying function of time, since it will implicitly contain $\exp(\gamma t)$.)

2.2 The Perturbed System

In the previous section we examined the behaviour of a system in the absence of driving terms. Here we consider the effect of an *externally* imposed current J_{ext} , in addition to the current given by equation 2.1.6. We shall assume that our unperturbed system is lossless; as a consequence σ is anti-hermitian and \mathbf{K} is hermitian. (Later we will include the effects of a loss mechanism.) Maxwell's equations can then be written:

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{E} + \mu_0 \partial \mathbf{H} / \partial t = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{H} - \epsilon_0 \partial \mathbf{E} / \partial t - \mathbf{J} = \mathbf{J}_{ext} \quad (2)$$

We restrict our attention to cases where \mathbf{J}_{ext} can in some sense be considered *small*. In that case the greatest response of the system will occur at the normal modes. The effect of the driving term will be to slowly modulate the amplitudes of the normal modes. If we consider a single mode at (\mathbf{k}, ω) , we write its electric field as:

$$\mathbf{E}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \text{Re} [E_0 u(\mathbf{r}, t) \exp(i\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{r} - \omega t)] \quad (3)$$

where E_0 is the unperturbed complex amplitude and u is the slowly varying (normalized) amplitude. We require that:

$$|\partial u / \partial t| \ll |\omega u| \quad (4)$$

$$|\partial u / \partial \mathbf{r}| \ll |\mathbf{k} u| \quad (5)$$

If we substitute (3) into equation 2.1.3 and expand u in a Taylor series:

$$u(\mathbf{r} - \mathbf{r}', t - t') \simeq u(\mathbf{r}, t) - \mathbf{r}' \cdot \partial u / \partial \mathbf{r} - t' \partial u / \partial t \quad (6)$$

(such an approximation is valid if $\sigma(\mathbf{r}', t')$ is some pulse like function about \mathbf{r}' , $t' = 0$) then equation 2.1.3 becomes:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{J}(\mathbf{r}, t) = \text{Re} [& (\sigma(\mathbf{k}, \omega) \cdot E_0 u + i \frac{\partial \sigma}{\partial \omega} \cdot E_0 \partial u / \partial t - \\ & - i \nabla u \cdot \frac{\partial}{\partial \mathbf{k}} (\sigma \cdot \mathbf{E})) \exp(i\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{r} - i\omega t)] \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

We allow other field quantities to vary as in equation 7. We can then use (4) and (5) as the basis of a perturbation expansion of Maxwell's equations. The first order equations, which include the variations on the scales of \mathbf{k} and ω , are the same as the unperturbed equations (2.1.7 and 2.1.8). The second order equations include the slow variations (the left hand sides of equations 4 and 5) and \mathbf{J}_{ext} . If we let \mathbf{J}_{ext} vary as:

$$J_{ext} = \text{Re} [J_D \exp(ik_D \cdot r - i\omega_D t)] \quad (8)$$

then by manipulating these second order equations (for details see reference Be1) we obtain the following equation for u :

$$(\partial/\partial t + v_D \cdot \nabla) u(r, t) = \frac{1}{4} E_0^* \cdot J_D / W_0 \times \\ \times \exp[i(k_D - k) \cdot r + i(\omega_D - \omega)t] \quad (9)$$

W_0 and v_D are defined in equations 2.1.13 and 2.1.14. Note that due to the presence of the exponential on the right hand side of (9) the assumption that u is slowly varying (equations 4 and 5) will only be valid if $(k_D, \omega_D) \simeq (k, \omega)$. As we shall see in the next section, this exponential also acts to reduce the strength of the interaction; so we would normally try to meet this condition on the frequency and wave number of J_{ext} . Loosely speaking, we say that the system responds most strongly if it is excited by an external current in *resonance* with one of its normal modes.

The extension to lightly damped waves is made by including $\sigma_h \cdot E$ in the second order equations. This current therefore is regarded as perturbing the undamped waves in the same way that J_{ext} does. For this reason the damping (or growth) term $\exp(\gamma t)$ is included in u in equation 3 and not E_0 ; i.e. E_0 is still time independent. The effect of $\sigma_h \cdot E$ is to add (γu) to the left hand side of (9).

The separation of current into J and J_{ext} in (2), might seem a rather artificial one. J_{ext} exists in the same region of space as J and in many cases is carried by the same current carriers. Yet such a separation is the heart of coupling of modes theory. It requires that we be able to take a complex system and break it up into simpler subsystems. So long as we are able to do this, coupling of modes will tell us how the subsystems interact, and so how the system as a whole operates. How this is done for nonlinear plasma problems is discussed below.

2.3 Application to Nonlinear Plasma Problems

A plasma is a nonlinear medium. However if the electric fields in it are small enough, it can be described by a set of *linearized* equations, in which case there exist in the plasma a continuum of normal modes satisfying the linear dispersion relation (equation 2.1.11). One of the properties of the normal modes of a linear system is that they are independent; the presence of one mode does not effect the behaviour of any other modes. For larger electric fields nonlinear effects come in, and the linearized equations no longer hold. Now, what used to be the normal modes, are no longer independent; they begin to *couple*. We shall take the following view of this coupling. Suppose there are two linear modes a and b at (k_a, ω_a) and (k_b, ω_b) , present in the plasma. As the amplitude of these modes is increased they will "mix" (borrowing the terminology of radio engineers) and produce currents at the sum and difference wave numbers and frequencies. We shall regard these currents as constituting the J_{ext} introduced in the last section. So if there exists a mode near, say, the sum wave number and frequency, it will be excited. Note that our unperturbed system consists of three linear modes of the plasma. The other modes are not part of this system; indeed it is they that produce the external driving current.

We shall now put some of the ideas expressed above on a more formal footing. We need a way of specifying the current J in the plasma, so as to include the nonlinear effects to second order. We shall write the current as a perturbation expansion:

$$J = J^{(1)} + J^{(2)} + \dots \quad (1)$$

where we neglect all terms of higher order than $J^{(2)}$ (we take $J^{(0)} = 0$). $J^{(1)}$ then is given by the linear σ as in equation 3, and we shall express $J^{(2)}$ as follows:

$$J_i^{(2)}(r, t) = \int_{\Omega} dr' \int_{\Omega} dr'' \int_{\Omega} dt' \int_{\Omega} dt'' \sigma_{ijk}(r-r', r-r'', t-t', t-t'') E_j(r', t') E_k(r'', t'') \quad (2)$$

Consistent with a calculation to second order, we may substitute *linear* electric fields into equation 2. If we express the linear electric field as a sum of slowly varying modes:

$$E(r, t) = \sum_m \text{Re} [E_{m0} u(r, t) \exp(ik_m \cdot r - i\omega_m t)] \quad (3)$$

then $J^{(2)}$ is given by:

$$J_i^{(2)} = \sum_{m,n} \text{Re} J_{m,n}^{(2)} u_m u_n \times \exp[i(k_m + k_n) \cdot r - i(\omega_m + \omega_n)t] \quad (4)$$

where:

$$J_{m,n}^{(2)} = \sigma_{ijk}(k_m, k_n, \omega_m, \omega_n) E_{m0j} E_{n0k} \quad (5)$$

where σ here has been properly transformed from the σ appearing in equation 2, and the sum is indicated over pairs of modes m and n ; but not counting n, m as well as m, n . The calculation of $J^{(2)}$ for a two fluid plasma is given in the next section.

We now restrict our attention to the case where only three waves (a, b and n) interact in the plasma. We assume that their frequencies and wave numbers satisfy:

$$(k_n, \omega_n) \simeq (k_a, \omega_a) + (k_b, \omega_b) \quad (6)$$

Remember that with our convention for mode amplitudes, each component of a mode, $E_n \exp[ik_n \cdot r - i\omega_n t]$, say, has a complex conjugate twin, $E_{-n} \exp[ik_{-n} \cdot r - i\omega_{-n} t]$, where $E_{-n} \equiv E_n^*$ and $(k_{-n}, \omega_{-n}) \equiv (-k_n^*, -\omega_n^*)$. Then when substituting for J_{ext} into equation 2.2.9, we keep only those terms for which the exponent on the right hand side is not rapidly varying. This leads to an equation for u_n :

$$\begin{aligned} (\partial/\partial t + v_\sigma \cdot \nabla + \gamma_n) u_n &\equiv du_n/dt = \\ &= K_n u_a u_b \exp(i \delta k \cdot r - i \delta \omega t) \end{aligned} \quad (7)$$

where:

$$K_n \equiv -\frac{1}{4} E_{n0}^* \cdot J_{ab}^{(2)}/W_{n0} \quad (8)$$

$$\delta k \equiv k_a + k_b - k_n \quad (9)$$

$$\delta \omega \equiv \omega_a + \omega_b - \omega_n \quad (10)$$

where W_{n0} is the energy density defined in equation 2.1.13. Similarly the equations for u_a and u_b are:

$$du_a/dt = K_a u_n u_b^* \exp(-i \delta k \cdot r + i \delta \omega t) \quad (11)$$

$$du_b/dt = K_b u_n u_a^* \exp(-i \delta k \cdot r + i \delta \omega t) \quad (12)$$

where K_a and K_b may be obtained from equation 8 by cyclicly permuting the mode subscripts thus: $a \rightarrow b \rightarrow -n \rightarrow a$.

Some very important relations hold for the action densities of these modes, in the special case where: $\delta k = 0$ and $\delta \omega = 0$. In this case, if the coupling conserves both energy and momentum, it can be shown [Lo1] that:

$$-\frac{dW_n/dt}{\omega_n} = \frac{dW_a/dt}{\omega_a} = \frac{dW_b/dt}{\omega_b} \quad (13)$$

These are the *Manley Rowe* relations. They are important for two reasons: firstly, they tell us how energy flows between the three modes; this is important if one is trying to heat a plasma by parametricly exciting a particular mode; and secondly they can be used to provide a relation between the various coupling coefficients (K in equations 7, 11 and 12). Bers shows [Be1]:

$$\left[\frac{E_n^* \cdot J_{ab}}{\omega_n} \right] = - \left[\frac{E_a^* \cdot J_{n-b}}{\omega_b} \right]^* = - \left[\frac{E_b^* \cdot J_{n-a}}{\omega_b} \right]^* \equiv M \quad (14)$$

So in order to calculate the complete solution of three waves interacting, it is only necessary to compute one coupling coefficient. Henceforth we shall refer to M as the coupling coefficient. Note too that any general expression for M must be symmetric with respect to a permutation of the modes a , b and $-n$. Expressing

equations 7, 11 and 12 in terms of M we obtain:

$$du_n/dt = -\frac{1}{4} \omega_n M/W_n u_a u_b \quad (15)$$

$$du_a/dt = \frac{1}{4} \omega_a M^*/W_a u_n u_b^* \quad (16)$$

$$du_b/dt = \frac{1}{4} \omega_b M^*/W_b u_n u_a^* \quad (17)$$

We now look at a particular case, in which one mode's amplitude is controlled externally, and so is held constant. Such a mode is usually called the "pump". We will choose this mode to be a . (It is more normal to call the mode at the sum frequency, in this case n , the pump. However we are primarily interested in the excitation of one of the other modes, viz. b , and the calculation of coupling coefficient then is more convenient if this mode is at the sum frequency. In the cases examined here the pump will always be at the highest frequency, so $\omega_b < 0$.) Since the amplitude of a is constant we can set $u_a = 1$. Then solving equations 14 and 16 for the case of no spatial variation, we find:

$$u_n \text{ and } u_b \sim \exp(\pm \gamma' t) \quad (18)$$

where:

$$\gamma'^2 = \gamma_0^2 - \gamma_b \gamma_n \quad (19)$$

$$\gamma_0^2 = -\omega_b \omega_n |M|^2 / (16 W_b W_n) \quad (20)$$

where γ_b and γ_n are the linear damping rates for modes b and n . In our collisionless fluid model, both these quantities are zero; so in most of what follows we concentrate on γ_0 , the growth rate in the absence of damping. Eventually, we will take damping rates from kinetic theory in order to calculate the *threshold condition*:

$$\gamma_0^2 = \gamma_b \gamma_n \quad (21)$$

Note that since γ_0 is directly proportional to the pump field E_{a0} , equation 21 is a condition on the pump strength. We note that growth of modes b and n is only possible if γ_0 is real. For positive energy modes, we see from equation 19 that we

must take ω_b and ω_n to be of opposite sign. But from equation 6, this is only possible if the pump (mode a) is at the highest (absolute) frequency.

If there is a slight frequency mismatch, i.e. if $\delta\omega \neq 0$, then the threshold for growth is increased; and equation 21 becomes:

$$\gamma_0^2 = \gamma_b \gamma_n + (\delta\omega)^2 \gamma_b \gamma_n / (\gamma_b + \gamma_n)^2 \quad (22)$$

2.4 Calculation of Second Order Current

We begin with our fluid equations (see section 1.3); for each species:

$$\partial n / \partial t + \nabla \cdot (n v) = 0 \quad (1)$$

$$m n (\partial / \partial t + v \cdot \nabla) v + \nabla p = n q (E + v \times B) \quad (2)$$

where the pressure p is given by the equation of state:

$$p = n_0 \kappa T (n/n_0)^\gamma \quad (3)$$

We will wish to calculate the current which is given by:

$$J = \sum_s q_s n_s v_s \quad (4)$$

Since we wish to solve for J in terms of E we also use one of Maxwell's equations:

$$\nabla \times E + \mu_0 \partial H / \partial t = 0 \quad (5)$$

We treat this rather complicated set of equations by expressing each quantity as a perturbation expansion, e.g.

$$n = n^{(0)} + n^{(1)} + n^{(2)} + n^{(3)} + \dots \quad (6)$$

where:

$$n^{(0)} \gg n^{(1)} \gg n^{(2)} \gg n^{(3)} \gg \dots \quad (7)$$

We take every zero order quantity ($n^{(0)}$ etc.) to be constant in both space and time. We examine here only problems in which $v^{(0)} = 0$ and $E^{(0)} = 0$, (i.e. no d.c. drift or electric field). Later we will resort to the usual subscript notation (B_0 , n_0 etc.) for zero order quantities. We substitute our perturbation expansions into equations

1 - 5, and separate them "by orders". (We expand the right hand side of (3) as a Taylor series about $n^{(0)}$, and eliminate p). The zero order equations are trivial, with $0 = 0$. The first order equations are the familiar linearized fluid equations:

$$\partial n^{(1)}/\partial t + n^{(0)} \nabla \cdot v^{(1)} = 0 \quad (8)$$

$$m n^{(0)} \partial v^{(1)}/\partial t - q n^{(0)} v^{(1)} \times B^{(0)} + m v_t^2 \nabla n^{(1)} = n^{(0)} q E^{(1)} \quad (9)$$

$$J^{(1)} = \sum_s q_s n_s^{(0)} v_s^{(1)} \quad (10)$$

where:

$$v_{ts}^2 \equiv \gamma \kappa T_s/m_s \quad (11)$$

and the second order equations are:

$$\partial n^{(2)}/\partial t + n^{(0)} \nabla \cdot v^{(2)} = R(r, t) \quad (12)$$

$$m n^{(0)} \partial v^{(2)}/\partial t - q n^{(0)} v^{(2)} \times B^{(0)} + m v_t^2 \nabla n^{(2)} = P(r, t) \quad (13)$$

$$J^{(2)} = \sum_s q(n^{(0)} v^{(2)} + n^{(1)} v^{(1)}) \quad (14)$$

where:

$$R(r, t) \equiv - \nabla \cdot (n^{(1)} v^{(1)}) \quad (15)$$

$$\begin{aligned} P(r, t) \equiv & - m n^{(0)} (v^{(1)} \cdot \nabla) v^{(1)} - m n^{(1)} \partial v^{(1)}/\partial t + q n^{(1)} E^{(1)} + \\ & + q n^{(1)} (v^{(1)} \times B^{(0)}) + q n^{(0)} (v^{(1)} \times B^{(1)}) - \\ & - (\gamma - 1) m v_t^2 n^{(1)} \nabla n^{(1)}/n^{(0)} \end{aligned} \quad (16)$$

We see that the first order equations (8 and 9) are a linear set of equations driven by the electric field on the right hand side of (9), and so are susceptible to solution by Fourier - Laplace transforming into wave vector - frequency space (as in equation 2.1.4). The second order equations (12 and 13) have left hand sides, which are the same as those in the first order case (with $^{(1)}$ becoming $^{(2)}$). These are driven by first order quantities, which we obtain by solving 8 and 9. So these equations can be solved in the same way the first order ones were. Note an interesting consequence of the perturbation scheme we have used, is that although the continuity equation obeys conservation of mass exactly (1), and

to first order (8), it does not at any higher order. R is a term expressing the creation of fluid by products of first order quantities, (it has the dimensions of number/time/ volume). P (the driving term for equation 9) is a rate of change of momentum term, arising, once again from products of first order quantities. Its dimensions are force/volume.

We now proceed to solve these equations beginning with the first order ones (8 and 9). As we have noted, these may be solved by transforms (as in equation 2.1.4). However for our purposes we find it somewhat more convenient to express the electric field as a sum of complex exponentials:

$$E^{(1)}(r, t) = \sum_a \text{Re}[E_a \exp(ik_a \cdot r - i\omega_a t)] \quad (17)$$

Making this assumption, and substituting this form into (8), (9) and (10), we find that for each mode a :

$$-i\omega_a n_a + n_0 ik_a \cdot v_a = 0 \quad (18)$$

$$\begin{aligned} -m n_0 i\omega_a v_a - q n_0 v_a \times B_0 + m v_1^2 ik_a n_a = \\ = n_0 q E_a \end{aligned} \quad (19)$$

$$J_a = \sum_s q n_0 v_a \quad (20)$$

where we have adopted the subscript notation for zero order quantities. All quantities with a mode subscript are assumed to be first order. We now have an *algebraic* set of linear equations, which can easily be solved (see reference St2):

$$n_a = k_a \cdot v_a / \omega_a \quad (21)$$

$$v_a = \sigma(k_a, \omega_a) \cdot E_a / (q n_0) \quad (22)$$

$$J_a = \sigma_{tot}(k_a, \omega_a) \cdot E_a \quad (23)$$

where:

$$\sigma_{tot} = \sum_s \sigma_s \quad (24)$$

$$\sigma(k, \omega) = i \epsilon_0 \omega_D^2 / \omega \wedge \Delta \quad (25)$$

$$\omega_D^2 \equiv n_0 q^2 / (\epsilon_0 m) \quad (26)$$

We take B_0 to be in the z direction ($B_0 = B_0 i_z$). When considering a single mode we can choose axes such that k lies in the x, z plane ($k = [k_x, 0, k_z] = k [\sin \theta, 0, \cos \theta] = k [\xi, 0, \zeta]$). In which case Δ and Λ are given by:

$$\Delta = \omega^2 - v_t^2 k^2 - \Omega^2 (\omega^2 - v_t^2 k_z^2) / \omega^2 \quad (27)$$

$$\Lambda_{xx} = \omega^2 - v_t^2 k_x^2 \quad (28)$$

$$\Lambda_{xy} = -\Lambda_{yx} = i \alpha (\omega^2 - v_t^2 k_z^2) \Omega / \omega \quad (29)$$

$$\Lambda_{xz} = \Lambda_{zx} = \omega^2 - v_t^2 k_x k_z \quad (30)$$

$$\Lambda_{yy} = \omega^2 - v_t^2 k^2 \quad (31)$$

$$\Lambda_{yz} = -\Lambda_{zy} = -i \alpha v_t^2 k_x k_z \Omega / \omega \quad (32)$$

$$\Lambda_{zz} = \omega^2 - v_t^2 k_z^2 - \Omega^2 \quad (33)$$

where:

$$\Omega = |q| B_0 / m \quad (34)$$

$$\alpha = \text{sgn } q \quad (35)$$

Two limits on B_0 are of particular interest to us, so before proceeding to the solution of the second order equations, we will give σ in these limits. The limits are $B_0 \rightarrow 0$, and $B_0 \rightarrow \infty$. For $B_0 \rightarrow 0$:

$$\sigma \rightarrow i \epsilon_0 \omega_D^2 \omega / (\omega^2 - v_t^2 k^2) \quad (36)$$

and for $B_0 \rightarrow \infty$:

$$\begin{aligned} \sigma_{ij} &\rightarrow i \epsilon_0 \omega_D^2 \omega / (\omega^2 - v_t^2 k_z^2) \quad \text{if } i = j = z \\ &\rightarrow 0 \quad \text{if } i \text{ or } j \neq z \end{aligned} \quad (37)$$

A more precise statement of the range of validity of these expressions will be made in section 3.2

We turn now to the solution of the second order equations (12) - (14). We have already remarked that these equations are driven by products of first order quantities. If we again assume that these are sums of modes as in equation 17, we

see that the right hand sides of equations 12, 13 and 14 will be convolutions of the linear modes; consequently the second order variables may also be expressed as a sum of complex exponentials. Writing down the equations for second order variations at (k_n, ω_n) , we find:

$$\begin{aligned} -i\omega_n n_n^{(2)} + n_0 ik_n \cdot v_n^{(2)} &= \sum_{a,b} R(k_a, \omega_a, k_b, \omega_b) \\ -m n_0 i\omega_n v_n^{(2)} - q n_0 v_n^{(2)} \times B_0 + m v_t^2 ik_n n_n^{(2)} &= \\ &= \sum_{a,b} P(k_a, \omega_a, k_b, \omega_b) \end{aligned} \quad (39)$$

$$J_n^{(2)} = \sum_s q n_0 v_n^{(2)} + \sum_{a,b} J(k_a, \omega_a, k_b, \omega_b) \quad (40)$$

where:

$$R \equiv \frac{1}{2} [-ik_n \cdot (n_a v_b) + a \leftrightarrow b] \quad (41)$$

[A]

$$\begin{aligned} P \equiv \frac{1}{2} [-m n^{(0)} (v_a \cdot ik_b) v_b + m n_a i\omega_b v_b + q n_a E_b + \\ + q n_a (v_b \times B^{(0)}) + q n^{(0)} (v_a \times B_b) - \\ - (\gamma-1) m v_t^2 n_a ik_b n_b/n^{(0)} + a \leftrightarrow b] \end{aligned} \quad (42)$$

$$J_c \equiv \frac{1}{2} [n_a v_b + a \leftrightarrow b] \quad (43)$$

[E]

where the sum is to be taken over linear modes satisfying:

$$(k_a, \omega_a) + (k_b, \omega_b) = (k_n, \omega_n) \quad (44)$$

Note that by the way we have defined R , P and J_c , including the symmetrization $a \leftrightarrow b$, the sum $\sum_{a,b}$ should only include each distinct pair of modes (a and b) once. The factors of $\frac{1}{2}$ appearing above are a consequence of our defining modes as the real parts of complex exponentials. The reader will notice that all the coefficients of n_a appearing in the definition of P occur also in the linear momentum equation (19). We can use this information to simplify the expression for P . We obtain:

$$\begin{aligned} P \equiv \frac{1}{2} [-m n^{(0)} (v_a \cdot ik_b) v_b + q n^{(0)} (v_a \times B_b) - \\ - (\gamma-1) m v_t^2 n_a ik_b n_b/n^{(0)} + a \leftrightarrow b] \end{aligned} \quad (45)$$

[B] [C] [D]

Again we end up with a linear set of algebraic equations, which can be solved to give $J_n^{(2)}$:

$$J_n^{(2)} = \sum_{a,b} \alpha_{ab} J_c + \sigma \cdot (P + m v_t^2 k_n R / \omega_n) / (q n_0) \quad (46)$$

Since we need to be able to refer to the various nonlinearities, we shall give them names:

$$A \quad \text{Continuity} \quad \nabla \cdot (n v) \quad (47)$$

$$B \quad \text{Convective} \quad (v \cdot \nabla) v \quad (48)$$

$$C \quad \text{Lorentz} \quad v \times B \quad (49)$$

$$D \quad \text{Pressure} \quad [\nabla n \gamma / n] \quad (50)$$

$$E \quad \text{Flowcurrent} \quad n v \quad (51)$$

where the letters A, B etc. refer to labels appearing by the definitions of R , P and J_c (equations 41, 45 and 43). On the right, we give the terms in the original fluid equations, that cause the nonlinearity. The term given for the pressure nonlinearity, however, does not appear in these equations. This is because it is made up of a sum of various terms in equation 42. We can obtain this term directly by dividing the momentum equation by n before expanding in the perturbation expansion. All of the waves we consider are adequately described by the electrostatic approximation (see section 3.1), in which we take $B^{(1)} = 0$. For this reason we will neglect the Lorentz nonlinearity from here on.

With $J_n^{(2)}$ we can calculate the coupling coefficient M . The MACSYMA form of M for the case where there is only a single pair of modes a and b is given in figure 1. (The symbols used here are explained in the notation section at the beginning of this thesis.) Note that we have already carried out the symmetrization ($a \leftrightarrow b$). Note too that in defining the MACSYMA variables for v and n , E has been replaced with k . This is admissible for, in the electrostatic limit k and E are parallel, so $E = k E/k$.

(C1) DISPLAY(MEL,MION);

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{CONTIN } \left(\frac{NE}{B} \left(\frac{KN}{N} \cdot VE \right) \left(\frac{VET}{N} \cdot \frac{KN}{WN} \right) \text{TERM2} + \frac{NE}{A} \left(\frac{KN}{N} \cdot VE \right) \left(\frac{VET}{N} \cdot \frac{KN}{WN} \right) \text{TERM1} \right) \\
 (E1) \text{ MEL} = & \frac{\text{CONVEC } \left(\left(\frac{KN}{A} \cdot VE \right) \left(\frac{VET}{N} \cdot VE \right) \text{TERM2} + \left(\frac{KN}{B} \cdot VE \right) \left(\frac{VET}{A} \cdot VE \right) \text{TERM1} \right)}{2 \frac{WN}{N}} \\
 & + \frac{\text{FLOWCUR } \left(\frac{NE}{B} \left(\frac{KN}{N} \cdot VE \right) \text{TERM2} + \frac{NE}{A} \left(\frac{KN}{N} \cdot VE \right) \text{TERM1} \right) \frac{NE}{A} \frac{NE}{B} \text{GM2} \left(\frac{VET}{N} \cdot \frac{KN}{N} \right) \text{PRESSURE}}{2 \frac{WN}{N}} \\
 & + \frac{\text{CONVEC } \left(\left(\frac{KN}{A} \cdot VI \right) \left(\frac{VIT}{N} \cdot VI \right) \text{TERM2} + \left(\frac{KN}{B} \cdot VI \right) \left(\frac{VIT}{A} \cdot VI \right) \text{TERM1} \right)}{2 \frac{WN}{N}} \\
 (E2) \text{ MION} = & \frac{\text{FLOWCUR } \left(\frac{NI}{B} \left(\frac{KN}{N} \cdot VI \right) \text{TERM2} + \frac{NI}{A} \left(\frac{KN}{N} \cdot VI \right) \text{TERM1} \right)}{2 \frac{WN}{N}} \\
 (D2) & \quad \quad \quad [E1, E2]
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 2.4.1 MACSYMA representation of the coupling coefficient

CHAPTER THREE
THE LINEAR WAVES

3.1 The Electrostatic Dispersion Relation

In section 2.1 we derived the electromagnetic dispersion relation for the natural modes of a system. With a conductivity appropriate for a plasma (see section 2.4) it will give every linear fluid mode of the plasma. As is well known electromagnetic phenomena arise because it takes a finite time for the effects of a potential at one point to be felt at another point. The speed at which such electromagnetic effects propagate is c , the speed of light. If a physical phenomenon takes place slowly enough then c may be regarded as infinite, and in that case the phenomenon can be described by the equations of statics. Such effects usually occur in two distinct regimes, in which either the magnetic fields or the electric fields play the dominant role. Woodson and Melcher [Wo1] discusses both cases, and derives the equations for them on the basis of time scale expansions. We are interested here in the second case, where the electric fields are the dominant ones and where the magnetic field can be ignored. Then equation 2.1.1 becomes:

$$\nabla \times \mathbf{E} \approx 0 \quad (1)$$

and the electric field is the gradient of a potential:

$$\mathbf{E} = -\nabla\phi \quad (2)$$

Gauss' law states:

$$\nabla \cdot \epsilon_0 \mathbf{E} = \rho \quad (3)$$

Also by charge continuity:

$$\partial\rho/\partial t + \nabla \cdot \mathbf{J} = 0 \quad (4)$$

Transforming into (\mathbf{k}, ω) space and eliminating ρ and \mathbf{J} using equations 4 and 2.1.6, equation 3 becomes:

$$\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{k} \Phi = 0 \quad (5)$$

where \mathbf{K} is defined in equation 2.1.10. The non-trivial solutions are given by:

$$K \equiv (\mathbf{k} \cdot \mathbf{K} \cdot \mathbf{k})/k^2 = 0 \quad (6)$$

This is the quasi electrostatic dispersion relation. It is exact only if equation 8 is exact, and this is only the case if \mathbf{E} is parallel to \mathbf{k} . But as Bers [Be1] shows, it is a good approximation as long as:

$$\omega^2/k^2 \ll c^2/|K_{ij}| \quad (7)$$

so we can expect the quasi electrostatic dispersion relation to give a satisfactory description for slow waves in regions where K_{ij} has no resonances.

In order to obtain an expression for the energy density, we need only take the general form (equation 2.1.13) and set H_0 to zero, and note that \mathbf{E}_0 and \mathbf{k} are parallel. If in addition we restrict ourselves to modes, such that $K = 0$, we find:

$$W = \frac{1}{4} \epsilon_0 |\mathbf{E}_0|^2 \partial K / \partial \omega \quad (8)$$

Substituting for \mathbf{K} (equation 2.1.10), and choosing axes such that:

$$\mathbf{k} = k [\xi, 0, \zeta] \quad (9)$$

where ξ and ζ are abbreviations for $\sin \theta$ and $\cos \theta$ respectively, the dispersion relation (6) becomes:

$$K = 1 - \sum_s R_s = 0 \quad (10)$$

where:

$$R_s = -i/\omega\epsilon_0 (\xi^2 \sigma_{xx} + 2 \xi \zeta \sigma_{xz} + \zeta^2 \sigma_{zz}) \quad (11)$$

For a warm species in a finite magnetic field σ is given by equation 2.3.25, and R_s is given by:

$$R_s = \omega_D^2 Q / (1 - v_t^2 k^2 Q) \quad (12)$$

where:

$$Q = \zeta^2/\omega^2 + \xi^2/(\omega^2 - \Omega^2) \quad (13)$$

3.2 Limits Giving Waves of Interest

The two limits we are particularly interested in are $B_0 \rightarrow \infty$, and $B_0 \rightarrow 0$. What happens to R_s in these limits is best seen by substituting the values of σ for these cases (equations 2.4.36 and 37). Then for $B_0 \rightarrow \infty$:

$$R_s \rightarrow \zeta^2 \omega_D^2 / (\omega^2 - v_t^2 k_z^2) \quad (1)$$

and for $B_0 \rightarrow 0$:

$$R_s \rightarrow \omega_D^2 / (\omega^2 - v_t^2 k^2) \quad (2)$$

Furthermore if the species is cold ($v_t \rightarrow 0$), then for $B_0 \rightarrow \infty$ (1) becomes:

$$R_s \rightarrow \zeta^2 \omega_D^2 / \omega^2 \quad (3)$$

and for $B_0 \rightarrow 0$ (2) becomes:

$$R_s \rightarrow \omega_D^2 / \omega^2 \quad (4)$$

Both lower hybrid and ion acoustic waves occur in a region where $\Omega_i \ll \omega \ll \Omega_e$, so it seems reasonable to take $B_0 \rightarrow \infty$ for electrons and $B_0 \rightarrow 0$ for the ions (we shall examine the exact conditions on the validity of these limits in a while). So taking ions to be cold our dispersion relation becomes:

$$1 - \frac{\omega_{Di}^2}{\omega^2} - \frac{\zeta^2 \omega_{De}^2}{\omega^2 - v_{te}^2 k_z^2} = 0 \quad (5)$$

For magnetosonic waves we may take $B_0 \rightarrow \infty$ for both ions and electrons, and in that case:

$$1 - \frac{\zeta^2 \omega_{Di}^2}{\omega^2} - \frac{\zeta^2 \omega_{De}^2}{\omega^2 - v_{te}^2 k_z^2} = 0 \quad (6)$$

For electrostatic ion cyclotron waves since $\omega \sim \Omega_i$ we must use equation 3.1.12 (with $v_t = 0$) to give R_i . The dispersion relation is:

$$1 - \omega_{Di}^2 \left[\frac{\zeta^2}{\omega^2} + \frac{\xi^2}{\omega^2 - \Omega_i^2} \right] - \frac{\zeta^2 \omega_{De}^2}{\omega^2 - v_{te}^2 k_z^2} = 0 \quad (7)$$

The validity of the above dispersion relations is found by examining the limits in which equations 3.1.12 and 13 give the same results. We see that the $B_0 \rightarrow 0$ limit requires only that $\omega^2 \gg \Omega^2$; (then $Q \simeq 1/\omega^2$). However the infinite magnetic field limit for which $Q \simeq \zeta^2/\omega^2$ requires that $\omega^2 \ll \Omega^2$ and $\omega^2 \ll \Omega^2 \zeta^2/\xi^2$. This latter condition is clearly a stringent one for small ζ (waves propagating close to perpendicular to the magnetic field) because then the major component of velocity is not along the z axis. As it turns out this second inequality imposes no extra conditions on the validity of the dispersion relation for magnetosonic waves (equation 6), because for these waves ω is proportional to ζ . On the other hand the inequality can be violated for lower hybrid modes; so if $\omega^2 \gg \Omega^2 \zeta^2/\xi^2$ (keeping $\omega^2 \ll \Omega^2$) equation 5 is replaced by:

$$1 - \frac{\omega_{Di}^2}{\omega^2} + \frac{\omega_{De}^2}{\Omega^2 + v_{te}^2 k_z^2} = 0 \quad (8)$$

We will look now for further approximations we can make to equations 5 and 8 to obtain dispersion relations for lower hybrid waves. We divide k space into the following regions: (a) $\zeta^2 \ll \omega^2/\Omega_e^2$, (b) $\omega^2/\Omega_e^2 \ll \zeta^2 \ll 1/\mu$ and (c) $1/\mu \ll \zeta^2$. (Region (b) exists because as we shall see $\omega = \omega_{Di}$ here, and we are considering plasmas with such a low β that $\Omega_e^2 \gg \omega_{De}^2$.) In (a) equation 8 is applicable; setting $k^2 \ll \Omega_e^2/v_{te}^2$ and $\omega^2 \ll \Omega_e^2/\mu$ we obtain:

$$\omega = \omega_{Di} \quad (9)$$

For region (b) equation 5 applies. Putting $k_z^2 \ll \omega^2/v_{te}^2$, we again obtain equation 9. Using equation 5 again in (c), with the same condition on k_z we obtain:

$$\omega = \zeta \omega_{De} \quad (10)$$

These dispersion relations may be used to convert the inequalities into conditions on ζ and k . We find that equation 9 is valid if:

$$\zeta^2 \ll 1/\mu \quad (11)$$

$$k^2 \ll \Omega_e^2/v_{te}^2 \quad (12)$$

$$\zeta^2 k^2 \ll \omega_{Di}^2/v_{te}^2 \quad (13)$$

similarly equation 10 is valid for:

$$\zeta^2 \gg 1/\mu \quad (14)$$

$$k^2 \ll \omega_{De}^2/v_{te}^2 \quad (15)$$

These conditions are summarized in figure 1, where for convenience the regions have been extended to where (11) to (15) become equalities.

Note that equations 9 and 10 above can be combined by allowing ζ to be arbitrary in equation 5, in which case the lower hybrid dispersion relation is:

$$\omega^2 = \omega_{Di}^2 (1 + \mu \zeta^2) \quad (16)$$

To obtain ion acoustic waves we begin with equation 5 and set $k_z^2 \gg \omega^2/v_{te}^2$ and $k^2 \ll \omega_{De}^2/v_{te}^2$:

$$\omega = k c_s \quad (17)$$

where

$$c_s^2 = v_{te}^2/\mu = \gamma \kappa T_e/m_i \quad (18)$$

and the conditions ζ and k are:

$$\zeta^2 \gg 1/\mu \quad (19)$$

$$\Omega_i^2 \ll k^2 c_s^2 \ll \omega_{Di} \quad (20)$$

These conditions are illustrated in figure 2.

A dispersion relation for magnetosonic waves can be obtained from equation 6 by letting $k_z^2 \gg \omega^2/v_{te}^2$ and $k^2 \ll \omega_{De}^2/v_{te}^2$:

$$\omega = k_z c_s \quad (21)$$

with the conditions on its validity being:

$$k^2 \zeta^2 \text{ and } k^2 \xi^2 \ll \Omega_i^2/c_s^2 \quad (22)$$

(see figure 3).

Figure 3.2.1 Regions of validity of dispersion relations for lower hybrid waves

Figure 3.2.2 Region of validity of ion acoustic dispersion relation $\omega = k c_s$

Figure 3.2.3 Region of validity of magnetosonic dispersion relation $\omega = k_z c_s$

By letting $k_z^2 \gg \omega^2/v_{te}^2$ and $k^2 \ll \omega_{pe}^2/v_{te}^2$ in equation 7 we obtain the dispersion relation for electrostatic ion cyclotron modes:

$$k^2 c_s^2 \left[\frac{\zeta^2}{\omega^2} + \frac{\xi^2}{\omega^2 - \Omega_i^2} \right] = 1 \quad (23)$$

We are usually interested in waves at fairly steep angles to the magnetic field (ζ small), because they are less damped here (see section 3.3). In which case the approximate dispersion relation is:

$$\omega^2 = \Omega_i^2 + k_x^2 c_s^2 \quad (24)$$

The dispersion diagrams for all these waves are given in figure 4. These may be compared with the results of Stringer [St4], in which he gives dispersion diagrams derived from the complete fluid dispersion relation, and approximate dispersion relations for various regions of (k, ω) space.

Waves derived from our fluid model are undamped; however in a real plasma, there will be collisional and collisionless, or Landau, damping. For the tokamak type plasmas we are interested in we can neglect collisional damping [Ar1]. Landau damping arises from the interaction of waves with particles, and is a function of the slope of the distribution function at ω/k_z [Kr1]. The condition that it be small for Maxwellian distributions is that $k_z v_t/(\omega - n \Omega)$ be far from unity for electrons and ions, (n is an integer). We shall examine this condition as it applies to the waves of interest in the next section.

Figure 3.2.4 Dispersion diagrams for waves of interest. (Arrows show the variation with increasing θ)

3.3 Characteristics of Waves

The lower hybrid mode is also a mode of a cold plasma. (We recall that to get its dispersion relation we set $k_z^2 v_{te}^2 \ll \omega^2$.) So we expect pressure to play little or no role in this mode. Since the ions are unmagnetized we expect their orbits to be nearly linear and along k . The electrons on the other hand are highly magnetized and for $\zeta = 0$ (perpendicular propagation), their dominant motion will be in the $E \times B$ (or y) direction. However, this is an electrostatic mode where the source of electric fields is charge bunching, and since E is parallel to k (equation 3.1.8), this motion will not contribute to the bunching. There is a small amount of ellipticity in the electron orbits, which allows them to partake in the charge bunching. At this point of course there is no component of the electron velocity along the z axis, and it was in this regime that we had to replace the infinite magnetic field dispersion relation (equation 3.2.5) with equation 3.2.8. As ζ is increased the z component of the electron velocity quickly dominates over the x component, (although not necessarily over the y component), in which case the infinite magnetic field limit is acceptable. The angle where the two components are contributing equally to the bunching is at $\zeta = \omega/\Omega_e$ (the borderline between the ranges of validity of equations 3.2.5 and 3.2.8). Note that as with all cold electrostatic plasma modes the frequency is a function of $i\mathbf{k}$ only (and not \mathbf{k}), so that the group velocity (equation 2.1.14) is perpendicular to \mathbf{k} . Carrying out the differentiation on equation 3.2.9 we find that for $\zeta^2 \ll 1/\mu$ the waves do not propagate ($v_\sigma = 0$); whereas for $\zeta^2 \gg 1/\mu$ (equation 3.2.10) we find:

$$v_\sigma = \xi \omega_{pe}/k [-\zeta, 0, \xi] \quad (1)$$

We have avoided the region of appreciable electron Landau damping by taking $k_z^2 v_{te}^2 \ll \omega^2$, so that the wave phase velocity lies well out on the tail of the electron distribution (the ion distribution is of course much narrower).

For ion acoustic waves as with lower hybrid waves the ions behave as though they were unmagnetized and the electrons as if they were infinitely magnetized. But now since $k_x^2 v_{te}^2 \gg \omega^2$, inertia plays no role in the electron force balance. Instead the picture is one where pressure is balanced by the electric forces on the electrons. For the ions, it is inertia that balances the electric field. Since we are in a region of (k, ω) space where a small charge separation produces large electric fields, the electric field may be regarded as a "glue" that ties the massive ions to a warm electron fluid. (However, it is an anisotropic glue which can allow relative motion perpendicular to k . As we have observed, the ions drift parallel to k and the electrons parallel to B_0 , so the effect of the electric field is to make $v_e \cdot k \approx v_i$, and the wave is then quasi-neutral.) So, an accurate picture of this wave is to consider it a sound wave where the inertia of the ions is balanced by the pressure of the electrons. This is borne out by observing that the phase velocity of this wave can be expressed in terms of electron temperature and ion mass (see equation 3.2.18). The γ that appears here is of course the exponent in the equation of state for the electrons ($p = p_0 (n/n_0)^\gamma$ see section 2.3). It is tempting to think of this quantity as a ratio of specific heats in analogy to sound propagation in a neutral gas. This would not, however be correct, for the electrons are not adiabatic in an ion sound wave. Indeed since their thermal velocity v_{te} is a square root of the mass ratio larger than c_s , they act as a good heat conductor, and so obey an isothermal gas law ($\gamma = 1$): The somewhat intuitive reasoning above is confirmed by kinetic theory (see, for instance reference Kr1). We see, from the dispersion relation for this wave, that its group velocity is equal to the phase velocity:

$$v_g = c_s \hat{k} \quad (2)$$

(note here the analogy with sound waves in a gas).

This mode avoids strong electron Landau damping because its phase velocity is much *less* than the electron thermal speed; (the actual condition is that $k_z^2 v_{te}^2 \gg \omega^2$, which was assumed in deriving the dispersion relation). Now however, there is the possibility of ion Landau damping. Note that if $T_i = T_e$, $c_s = v_{ti}$, and the wave would not exist as a well defined mode. So for the wave to be lightly damped we require that the ion temperature be several times less than the electron's. We can also improve matters by taking k to be at a fairly steep angle to the magnetic field, because ion Landau damping is an increasing function of $v_{ti}^2 k_z^2 / \omega^2 \sim \zeta^2$. These conditions are best illustrated on a ω, k_z diagram (see figure 1)

Electrostatic ion cyclotron waves are an extension of the ion acoustic dispersion relation to nearer Ω_i , so we expect the general nature of the waves to be very similar. Now the ion orbits cannot be considered parallel to k ; indeed at frequencies close to Ω_i the ions are being driven close to one their resonances, and their orbits become large and circular. Ion cyclotron and ion Landau damping are again shown in figure 1. However kinetic theory predicts a wave such that $2 \Omega_i > \omega > \Omega_i$, even when $T_i \sim T_e$ [Te1]. This occurs at angles around $83^\circ - 86^\circ$. At such angles equation 3.2.24 is the appropriate dispersion relation, and the group velocity is then:

$$v_{\sigma} = k_x c_s^2 / \omega i_x \quad (3)$$

Magnetosonic waves are the counterpart of ion acoustic waves below the ion cyclotron frequency. The ion orbits this time are along the magnetic field, and as we saw (equation 3.2.21) this modifies the dispersion relation so that ω is only a function of k_z . As a consequence the group velocity is also along the z axis:

$$v_{\sigma} = c_s i_z \quad (4)$$

Figure 3.3.1 Regions of heavy damping for electrostatic ion cyclotron and ion acoustic waves

3.4 Resonance Conditions

We have seen that three wave nonlinear interactions are strongest if the waves satisfy certain resonance conditions:

$$k_n = k_a + k_b \quad (1)$$

$$\omega_n = \omega_a + \omega_b \quad (2)$$

The convention we adopt is as follows: a is the externally driven pump; b is an "idler" mode, and n is the signal (some low frequency mode we are trying to excite). The waves we consider are all positive energy, so the condition that the pump give up energy to the low frequency modes means that ω_a has to be the highest frequency (see section 2.3). As a consequence, we must choose $\omega_b < 0$. (What we are saying here is merely that in order to drive mode n , the pump must mix with the complex conjugate half of the idler.) As was pointed out in section 2.3 the three wave interaction with one wave (the pump) at constant amplitude, is driven by two nonlinear processes (the pump and idler combining to drive the signal, and the pump and signal driving the idler), each of which has its own coupling coefficient. However for the conservative resonant interactions we consider here, the Manley - Rowe relations (equation 2.3.14) provide a way of getting from one to the other. So we concentrate here on the excitation of the signal by the pump and idler.

The first task then in trying to satisfy the resonance conditions is to decide which waves we wish to couple. There are two classes of interactions we examine:

- 1) A lower hybrid wave (the pump) and two ion acoustic waves (the idler and signal)
- 2) Two lower hybrid waves (the pump and idler) and a low frequency wave, which may be electrostatic ion cyclotron or magnetosonic .

We shall use the approximate dispersion relations derived in section 3.2; this relieves us of the necessity of solving high order polynomials. Now we have 12 unknowns (the k 's and ω 's of the three modes) with 7 equations (4 resonance conditions and 3 dispersion relations); so there are 5 free parameters that we may choose. Of these, only 4 are nontrivial, since the fifth amounts to nothing more than a choice of axes. (We choose the pump wave vector to lie in the x, z plane) Having chosen these parameters, we may calculate k, ω for each mode. Finally, we should go back and check that the approximations we made in deriving the dispersion relations are still valid, and that the modes are not heavily damped. The plasma we consider is one in which β is low and $\omega_{Di} \gg \Omega_i$ (see section 1.3).

Considering the case of coupling to ion acoustic waves, we note that for the pump $\omega > \omega_{Di}$, and for ion acoustic waves $\omega^2 \ll \omega_{Di}^2$. Remembering that $\omega_n = \omega_a + \omega_b$, we see that the second inequality is best satisfied if $|\omega_{b,n}| \simeq \omega_a/2$ and $\omega_a \simeq \omega_{Di}$. Thus we use the dispersion relation $\omega = \omega_{Di}$ for the pump (equation 3.2.9, valid for $\xi^2 \ll 1/\mu$). For the idler and signal (modes b and n) we use the ion acoustic dispersion relation $\omega = k c_s$ (equation 3.2.17). We begin by choosing k_a ; then using the dispersion relations and equations 1 and 2, we find $k_n + (-k_b) = k_a$ and $|k_n| + |-k_b| = \omega_a/c_s$. Thus the locus of k_n is an ellipsoid with k_a spanning the foci (see figure 1). (Note, however, that certain regions are forbidden to k_n and k_b , since the dispersion relation is no longer valid (see figure 3.2.2). Then k_b and k_n are determined by choice of (say) the direction cosines of k_n . It is slightly more convenient to choose α and β , as defined in figure 2(a). Thus the five parameters we choose are: k_a ($k_{ax}, k_{ay} = 0, k_{az}$), α and β . A typical case is shown in figure 2.

We come now to the excitation of an electrostatic ion cyclotron or

Figure 3.4.1 Locus of \bar{k}_n for a given \bar{k}_a for coupling to two ion acoustic waves

(a)

(b)

Figure 3.4.2 Coupling to ion acoustic waves.
 (a) in \bar{k} space, (b) in ω, k space

magnetosonic mode. In this case we consider the pump to be above the lower hybrid frequency, an idler nearby (in frequency) and the signal (the electrostatic ion cyclotron or magnetosonic mode) at a considerably lower frequency. We describe the pump and idler by the dispersion relation $\omega^2 = \omega_{Di}^2 (1 + \mu \zeta^2)$ (equation 3.2.16). Since $\omega_n \ll \omega_a$, $\omega_b \sim -\omega_a$ and $\cos^2 \theta_a \sim \cos^2 \theta_b$. There are two possibilities: either the z components of k_a and k_b are of opposite sign, or they have the same sign. These are shown in figure 3 (keeping ω_a and k_n fixed). Note that in the first case (a) k_{az} is much larger than in the second (b). So the pump in the first case is far more likely to be electron Landau damped (see section 3.3). Note that we cannot take k_{nz} arbitrarily small; for then the electrostatic ion cyclotron wave would be ion - cyclotron damped (see figure 3.3.1); and the magnetosonic wave would have a very low frequency, and by the Manley - Rowe relations (equation 2.3.13) the efficiency of energy conversion would be very poor. Similar considerations usually force us to take ω_a somewhat above ω_{Di} (although we cannot take it too high, or the efficiency of the down - conversion is impaired). In the numerical examples in section 4.2, we take $\omega_a = 3 \omega_{Di}$. Therefore $\cos^2 \theta_a \gg \mu^{-1}$ in all the cases we consider. Contrast this with the case of coupling to ion acoustic waves, where the opposite inequality held.

The five parameters that are convenient to choose in this case are: ω_a , $k_{ay} = 0$, and k_n . A typical interaction involving an electrostatic ion cyclotron wave is illustrated in figure 4. The reader's attention is drawn to the definition of ψ in this figure. This angle turns out to be an important one for these interactions, since it determines the degree to which the $E \times B$ induced electron velocity by the pump is utilized. An important difference occurs between coupling to electrostatic ion cyclotron and magnetosonic waves, in the size of ψ . Since k_n is usually much smaller for the magnetosonic wave, it is not possible to make ψ as large as with the

Figure 3.4.3 Two possible configurations for coupling to electrostatic ion cyclotron and magnetosonic waves.
 (a) k_{az} and k_{bz} have opposite signs,
 (b) k_{az} and k_{bz} have the same sign.

Figure 3.4.4 Coupling to electrostatic ion cyclotron waves. (a) in \bar{k} space, (b) in ω, k space

electrostatic ion cyclotron wave. This changes the dominant mechanism of the interaction. This point is discussed in section 4.5.

Using MACSYMA and our approximate dispersion relations we have been able to solve analytically in each case for (k, ω) for the three modes in terms of the parameters we chose. Further we have written programs in MACSYMA that take these expressions for (k, ω) , request numerical values for the parameters, and return numerical values for (k, ω) . We have utilized these programs in the numerical work described in section 4.2.

CHAPTER FOUR
CALCULATION OF GROWTH RATES

4.1 Use of MACSYMA

Much of the work described in this thesis was done on an algebraic computational system called MACSYMA (Project *MAC*'s *SY*mbolic *M*anipulator). Because of this, and because this work constitutes some of the first plasma physics work to be done on this system, I shall take some time to describe MACSYMA. The interested reader is referred to the MACSYMA manual [Bo1], and to John Kulp's masters thesis [Ku1], which describes many of the applications of symbolic manipulation systems to plasma physics problems. Other examples of work on MACSYMA can be found in references Be2 and Ku2. The appendix contains a list of the MACSYMA functions that appear in this thesis. The examples of MACSYMA work that appear in here, were done on versions 233 to 236.

MACSYMA is a large computer program (about 150,000 words of code, at present) written in LISP [Mc1], that is being developed by the Mathlab group of Project MAC, M.I.T. It is capable of handling analytic expressions involving numbers, symbolic variables, matrices, functions and other entities. It can perform many operations on such expressions, including simplification, substitution, differentiation and integration, solution of equations and the taking of limits. MACSYMA runs under the ITS time sharing system [Ea1] on a DEC PDP-10 computer at Project MAC. It is designed to be run from consoles, and to allow the user to interact with the program.

To illustrate a few of the capabilities of MACSYMA and to acquaint the reader with some of its conventions, I have given an example of a console session,

with comments interspersed. MACSYMA input and output in this example are in upper case. The lines typed by the user are labelled C_i , and MACSYMA responds in lines labelled D_i and E_i . The user tells MACSYMA to execute a command by terminating his command string (in line C_i) with a ";" or a "\$", ";" indicating that the result of executing the command should be displayed as line D_i and "\$" causing the display of the result to be suppressed, (although it can still be referred to as D_i).

In line C_1 we type in "G:" followed by an expression, using a FORTRAN type syntax ("↑" replacing "**"). ":" is the operator used to to assign names to expressions. So in this example we have given the expression to the right of the ":" the name G. MACSYMA returns the expression as a two dimensional display in line D_1 .

(C1) G: X↑3-A↑3;

(D1)
$$\begin{array}{cc} 3 & 3 \\ X & - A \end{array}$$

After executing line C_i and returning the result in D_i , the next input - output pair of lines is labelled $C_{(i+1)}$ and $D_{(i+1)}$. In line C_2 we type in an expression involving G. MACSYMA evaluates the expression (substituting for G) and returns the result in D_2 .

(C2) 1/G↑2;

(D2)
$$\begin{array}{c} 1 \\ \hline 3 \quad 3 \quad 2 \\ (X - A) \end{array}$$

We now ask MACSYMA to find the roots of $G = 0$. The way we do this is with the function SOLVE. This is a function of two arguments, the first of which is the equation to be solved, and the second is the value one wants to solve for. The result is a list of equations, giving the solutions. (The solutions are given in lines labelled E_i .) %I is the square root of -1 (or i).

(C3) SOLVE(G=0,X);
SOLUTION

$$(E3) \quad X = \frac{\%I \text{ SQRT}(3) A - A}{2}$$

$$(E4) \quad X = -\frac{\%I \text{ SQRT}(3) A + A}{2}$$

$$(E5) \quad X = A$$

(D5) [E3, E4, E5]

We can check one of these solutions, e.g. E3, by substituting it back into the original expression D1, using the function SUBST. (Note that an expression can be referenced by its line label, as well as by its name. This relieves us of the necessity of always giving names to expressions.)

(C6) SUBST(E3,D1);

$$(D6) \quad \frac{(\%I \text{ SQRT}(3) A - A)^3}{8} - A^3$$

Note that the answer in D6 is not 0, because MACSYMA doesn't know how we want the answer. In this case we clearly need to expand the cube in D6. The function is EXPAND. "%" always refers to the last D line (in this case D6), irrespective of whether or not it was displayed.

(C7) EXPAND(%);

(D7) 0

We now ask MACSYMA to integrate F(D1) with respect to X. Since F is some (as yet) undefined function, it can't perform the integral, and returns it unevaluated.

(C8) INTEGRATE(F(G),X);

(D8)
$$\int F(X^3 - A^3) DX$$

So before we can go further we must tell MACSYMA the definition of F. This is done in C9; " := " is the operator used for functional definitions. We have chosen to define F as the inverse function. Then we invoke an integration again in C10. Since the form of the result depends on whether or not A is zero, MACSYMA asks the user for this information.

(C9) F(Z) := 1/Z;

(D9)
$$F(Z) := \frac{1}{Z}$$

(C10) EV(D8, INTEGRATE);
IS A ZERO OR NONZERO?

NONZERO;

(D10)
$$-\frac{\frac{\text{LOG}(X^2 + AX + A^2)}{6A^2}}{\frac{\text{SQRT}(3)A^2}} - \frac{\text{ATAN}\left(\frac{2X + A}{\text{SQRT}(3)A}\right)}{\frac{\text{SQRT}(3)A^2}} + \frac{\text{LOG}(X - A)}{3A^2}$$

The result (D10) can be checked by differentiation with respect to X (C11).

(C11) DIFF(%,X);

(D11)
$$-\frac{\frac{2}{3A^2} \frac{(2X + A)^2}{\left(\frac{(2X + A)^2}{3A^2} + 1\right)}}{\frac{3A^2}{3A^2}} - \frac{\frac{2X + A}{6A^2} \frac{2}{(X^2 + AX + A^2)^2}}{\frac{3A^2}{3A^2}} + \frac{1}{3A^2} \frac{1}{(X - A)^2}$$

But it is not easy to see that D11 is the same as the original integrand. By rationally simplifying D11 (C12), we see that indeed we have recovered the integrand.

(C12) RATSIMP(%);

(D12)

$$\frac{1}{X^3 - A^3}$$

A data structure, we make great use of in the examples that follow, is the subscripted array. Subscripted arrays provide the convenience of allowing us to refer to a collection of expressions by a single name (the array name). A single expression or "element" of an array can be referenced by following the array name by a list of subscripts in square brackets (C13). The subscripts are displayed as such by the MACSYMA displayer (D13).

(C13) ARRAYNAME [SUBSCRIPT1, SUBSCRIPT2];

(D13) ARRAYNAME
 SUBSCRIPT1, SUBSCRIPT2

Values may be given to the elements of an array, either individually by using the ":" operator, or by using an associated function definition (i.e. by using ":="), as in C14. When we ask for the value of the Q'th element of A (C15), this definition is invoked and the value of the element returned (D15). The definition in C14 differs from a normal function definition (e.g. C9), in that once a particular element of an array has been calculated, its value is stored and that element is not normally re-computed. This has obvious advantages, when a few elements occur repeatedly in the course of a calculation.

(C14) A[I] := 5*I;

(D14)

$$A := 5 I$$

(C15) A[Q];

(D15)

$$5 Q$$

A function that has proved extremely useful in the work described in this thesis is TAYLOR. TAYLOR($f(x)$, x , x_0 , pow) generates a Taylor series of $f(x)$ in x

about x_0 , and truncating the series at $(x-x_0)^{1pow}$. The result is put in a special internal form that contains information on the level of truncation. This information is preserved in most operations between Taylor series and other forms. Using this capability we have been able to carry out expansions of expressions in the various large and small parameters of the problem. We shall illustrate the use of TAYLOR in the following example.

In C16 we define an expression S1; and in C17 we take its Taylor series (T1). Note that the result in D17 is displayed in a special way. Firstly, there is an /R/ next to the line label; this indicates that internally this expression is in rational form (an efficient form for polynomials). Secondly the expression itself includes ". . .", to remind the user that he is dealing with a Taylor series; (these are omitted if the series has only one term).

```
(C16) S1:SQRT(1-10*SIN(X))*COSH(X);
(D16)                                COSH(X) SQRT(1 - 10 SIN(X))

(C17) T1:TAYLOR(S1,X,0,2);
(D17)/R/                               2
                                     1 - 5 X - 12 X + . . .
```

In C18 we square the Taylor series. Note that the result is still a Taylor series, and that it has been truncated at the same level as the original Taylor series.

```
(C18) T1^2;
(D18)/R/                               2
                                     1 - 10 X + X + . . .
```

In C20 we add an expression in general representation (D19) to T1. The Taylor series representation is "contagious", and so forces its conventions onto the added piece. One consequence of this is the dropping of the $X^{3/4}$ term of D19.

(C19) 3+X↑2+X↑3/4;

$$(D19) \quad \frac{X^3}{4} + X^2 + 3$$

(C20) T1+%;

$$(D20) /R/ \quad 4 - 5 X - 11 X^2 + \dots$$

There are a number of ways to prevent this truncation from occurring, two of which are shown here. EV (C21) merely removes the truncation level; whereas RATDISREP converts the Taylor series into the general representation.

(C21) EV(T1)+D19;

$$(D21) /R/ \quad \frac{X^3 - 44 X^2 - 20 X + 16}{4}$$

(C22) RATDISREP(T1)+D19;

$$(D22) \quad \frac{X^3}{4} - 11 X^2 - 5 X + 4$$

Below is a case, where it is necessary to reset the truncation level. The lowest order term in the Taylor series in D24 (T2) is not of order unity; and so when we square it (C25), we obtain 0. T2's truncation level can however be reset using TAYLOR (C26), to obtain an answer that is correct to as many significant terms as T2 (i.e. 2).

(C23) S2:X↑2*S1;

$$(D23) \quad X^2 \text{ COSH}(X) \text{ SQRT}(1 - 10 \text{ SIN}(X))$$

(C24) T2:TAYLOR(S2,X,0,3);

$$(D24) /R/ \quad X^2 - 5 X^3 + \dots$$

(C25) %↑2;

$$(D25) /R/ \quad 0$$

```
(C26) TAYLOR(T2,X,0,5)↑2;
(D26) /R/
      4      5
X  - 10 X  + . . .
```

This section was intended to give the reader enough familiarity with MACSYMA to understand the examples that follow. The appendix can be consulted for a brief description of the other MACSYMA functions used in this thesis; but the reader should refer to the MACSYMA manual for a full description of these functions.

4.2 *Numerical Calculation*

The complexity of the problem at hand dictated a rather tortuous path towards its solution. On one hand we were dealing with a problem where we had little feeling for the magnitudes of the quantities involved; and on the other we were dealing with MACSYMA, a system in which we had little experience. For this reason we decided to invest some effort into using MACSYMA to calculate numerical results for the growth rates. The emphasis was on performing the calculation in such a way that dominant effects could be traced back to things we understood, such as linear velocities and densities.

Early attempts at numerical calculation of growth rates were inefficient for two reasons. Firstly, we used a normalization scheme that left some symbolic variables in the expressions for conductivity. Since our expressions then contained these symbolic variables in their denominators, MACSYMA was trying to be clever about looking for greatest common divisors, and calculations were running very slowly; a more sensible approach would have been to notice that the constants could have been taken out of the expression, (for instance by appropriately normalizing quantities) as a common factor, and to have performed the calculation on expressions involving numbers only.

The second mistake we made that led to inefficiencies was that we started with the expression for the coupling coefficient involving only conductivities and electric fields. In such an expression there are several common sub-expressions, corresponding to velocities and densities. So in the program as originally run, MACSYMA had to calculate these quantities several times. We corrected this by using the expression for the coupling coefficient in terms of velocities and densities, and calculating these quantities prior to the main calculation.

Figure 1 shows an example of MACSYMA output, illustrating the numerical calculation. (The symbols in this figure are given in the notation section at the beginning of this thesis; a list of MACSYMA functions appearing here is given in the appendix, with a brief explanation of each.) In all the examples of this section we assume a highly magnetized hydrogen plasma, for which: $\omega_{pi}/\Omega_i (= WN[PI]) = 10$ and $m_e/m_i (= MU) = 1836$. Since $\Omega_e^2/\omega_{pe}^2 \gg 1$, $\omega_{lh} \sim \omega_{pi}$. In line C1 we set various switches to the appropriate value for doing numerical work (see the appendix for details). In line C2 we load a file containing the general expression for the electron and ion terms of the coupling coefficient (MEL and MION see figure 2.4.1); and we display them in D3 and D4. Note that these expressions contain dummy variables TERM1, CONVEC, CONTIN, etc., whose purpose is to identify the various parts of the expressions, as the calculation proceeds. Eventually these quantities will be set to unity. Numerical values for the frequencies and wave numbers of the three modes are loaded (C5), and displayed (E8 - E13). The general expression for the conductivity of a warm fluid species is loaded (C14); specialization is made to electrons (C15 - C16), and the resulting expression is used as a basis for an associated function definition (C18). The quantities VE, NE and VET are defined (C20 - C22) and displayed (E24 - E28). Matrix multiplication is disabled (C29), and the electron term of the coupling coefficient is evaluated and displayed (C30 -

(C1) (LINEL:95,TIME:TRUE,RATMX:FALSE,DOTASSOC:FALSE,FLOAT:TRUE,NUMER:TRUE,
DOMXMXOPS:FALSE,DOALLMXOPS:TRUE,NOLABELS:TRUE)\$

TIME= 35 MSEC.

(C2) LOADFILE (SYMCC,NEWS,DSK,PLASMA)\$

SYMCC NEWS DSK PLASMA BEING LOADED
LOADING DONE
TIME= 694 MSEC.

(C3) MEL;
TIME= 1 MSEC.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{CONTIN } \left(\begin{matrix} \text{KN} \\ \text{N} \end{matrix} \right) \left(\begin{matrix} \text{NE} & \text{KN} & \text{VE} \\ \text{B} & \text{N} & \text{A} \end{matrix} \right) \left(\begin{matrix} \text{VET} & \text{---} \\ \text{N} & \text{WN} \end{matrix} \right) \text{TERM2} + \left(\begin{matrix} \text{KN} \\ \text{N} \end{matrix} \right) \left(\begin{matrix} \text{NE} & \text{KN} & \text{VE} \\ \text{A} & \text{N} & \text{B} \end{matrix} \right) \left(\begin{matrix} \text{VET} & \text{---} \\ \text{N} & \text{WN} \end{matrix} \right) \text{TERM1} \\
 (D3) & \text{-----} \\
 & \qquad \qquad \qquad \begin{matrix} 2 \text{ WN} \\ \text{N} \end{matrix} \\
 & \text{CONVEC } \left(\begin{matrix} \text{KN} & \text{VE} \\ \text{A} & \text{B} \end{matrix} \right) \left(\begin{matrix} \text{VET} & \text{VE} \\ \text{N} & \text{A} \end{matrix} \right) \text{TERM2} + \left(\begin{matrix} \text{KN} & \text{VE} \\ \text{B} & \text{A} \end{matrix} \right) \left(\begin{matrix} \text{VET} & \text{VE} \\ \text{N} & \text{B} \end{matrix} \right) \text{TERM1} \\
 + & \text{-----} \\
 & \qquad \qquad \qquad \begin{matrix} 2 \text{ MU WN} \\ \text{N} \end{matrix} \\
 & \text{FLOWCUR } \left(\begin{matrix} \text{NE} & \text{KN} & \text{VE} \\ \text{B} & \text{N} & \text{A} \end{matrix} \right) \text{TERM2} + \left(\begin{matrix} \text{NE} & \text{KN} & \text{VE} \\ \text{A} & \text{N} & \text{B} \end{matrix} \right) \text{TERM1} \quad \begin{matrix} \text{NE} & \text{NE} & \text{GM2} & \text{VET} & \text{KN} \\ \text{A} & \text{B} & & \text{N} & \text{N} \end{matrix} \text{PRESSURE} \\
 + & \text{-----} + \text{-----} \\
 & \qquad \qquad \qquad \begin{matrix} 2 \text{ WN} \\ \text{N} \end{matrix} \qquad \qquad \qquad \begin{matrix} 2 \text{ WN} \\ \text{N} \end{matrix}
 \end{aligned}$$

(C4) MION;
TIME= 1 MSEC.

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \text{CONVEC } \left(\begin{matrix} \text{KN} & \text{VI} \\ \text{A} & \text{B} \end{matrix} \right) \left(\begin{matrix} \text{VIT} & \text{VI} \\ \text{N} & \text{A} \end{matrix} \right) \text{TERM2} + \left(\begin{matrix} \text{KN} & \text{VI} \\ \text{B} & \text{A} \end{matrix} \right) \left(\begin{matrix} \text{VIT} & \text{VI} \\ \text{N} & \text{B} \end{matrix} \right) \text{TERM1} \\
 (D4) & \text{-----} \\
 & \qquad \qquad \qquad \begin{matrix} 2 \text{ WN} \\ \text{N} \end{matrix} \\
 & \text{FLOWCUR } \left(\begin{matrix} \text{NI} & \text{KN} & \text{VI} \\ \text{B} & \text{N} & \text{A} \end{matrix} \right) \text{TERM2} + \left(\begin{matrix} \text{NI} & \text{KN} & \text{VI} \\ \text{A} & \text{N} & \text{B} \end{matrix} \right) \text{TERM1} \\
 & \text{-----} \\
 & \qquad \qquad \qquad \begin{matrix} 2 \text{ WN} \\ \text{N} \end{matrix}
 \end{aligned}$$

(C5) LOADFILE (VALWK,1,DSK,CFK)\$

VALWK 1 DSK CFK BEING LOADED
LOADING DONE
TIME= 513 MSEC.

(C6) (KN[I]:=[KNX[I],KNY[I],KNZ[I]],MU:1836,GM2:-1)\$
TIME= 29 MSEC.

Figure 4.2.1 (i) Example of numerical calculation.

```

(C7) DISPLAY(WN[A],KN[A],WN[B],KN[B],WN[N],KN[N])$
(E8)                                     WN = 30
                                         A
(E9)                                     KN = [1.22130355, 0, 0.080794234]
                                         A
(E10)                                    WN = - 28.1895313
                                         B
(E11)                                    KN = [- 1.22130355, 1.5, 0.119205762]
                                         B
(E12)                                    WN = 1.81046867
                                         N
(E13)                                    KN = [0, 1.5, 0.2]
                                         N
TIME= 132 MSEC.

(C14) LOADFILE(SIG,WARM,DSK,PLASMA)$
SIG WARM DSK PLASMA BEING LOADED
LOADING DONE
TIME= 709 MSEC.

(C15) (WN[C]:MU,WN[P]:SQRT(MU)*WN[PI])$
TIME= 45 MSEC.

(C16) SIG:EV(SIGMAN[I])$
TIME= 1598 MSEC.

(C17) KILL(SIGMAN)$
TIME= 5 MSEC.

(C18) SIGMAN[I]:='SIG$
TIME= 9 MSEC.

(C19) KILL(SIG)$
TIME= 5 MSEC.

(C20) VE[K]:=-EV(SIGMAN[K].KN[K],EVAL,EXPAND)$
TIME= 20 MSEC.

(C21) NE[K]:=EV(KN[K].(VE[K]/WN[K]),EVAL,EXPAND)$
TIME= 29 MSEC.

(C22) VET[K]:=EV(KN[K].SIGMAN[K],EVAL,EXPAND)$
TIME= 15 MSEC.

(C23) DISPLAY(VE[A],VE[B],NE[A],NE[B],VET[N])$

```

Figure 4.2.1 (ii) Example of numerical calculation.

(ROW TO COL CONVERSION MADE)

```

      [ 0.020214025 ]
      [               ]
(E24) VE = [ - 1.23709832 %I ]
      A [               ]
      [ - 5.0072172 ]

```

(ROW TO COL CONVERSION MADE)

```

      [ 1.5480223 %I + 0.0193519525 ]
      [                               ]
(E25) VE = [ 1.2604034 %I - 0.0237679875 ]
      B [                               ]
      [ 8.0106107 - 7.4505806E-9 %I ]

```

```

(E26) NE = - 0.01266222726
      A

```

```

(E27) NE = 3.1506453E-11 %I - 0.031771524
      B

```

```

(E28) VET = [ - 0.07008022 %I 6.9105678E-5 - 9.4757886 ]
      N

```

TIME= 5604 MSEC.

```

(C29) DOALLMXOPS:FALSE$
TIME= 4 MSEC.

```

```

(C30) MEL:EV(MEL,EVAL)$
TIME= 1672 MSEC.

```

(C31) DISPTERMS(MEL)\$

+

```

      [ 1.5480223 %I + 0.0193519525 ]
      [                               ]
1.50420253E-4 CONVEC (([1.22130355, 0, 0.080794234] . [ 1.2604034 %I - 0.0237679875 ] )
      [                               ]
      [ 8.0106107 - 7.4505806E-9 %I ]

```

```

      [ 0.020214025 ]
      [               ]
([ - 0.07008022 %I 6.9105678E-5 - 9.4757886 ] . [ - 1.23709832 %I ] ) TERM2
      [               ]
      [ - 5.0072172 ]

```

```

      [ 0.020214025 ]
      [               ]
+ ([ - 1.22130355, 1.5, 0.119205762] . [ - 1.23709832 %I ] )
      [               ]
      [ - 5.0072172 ]

```

```

      [ 1.5480223 %I + 0.0193519525 ]
      [                               ]
([ - 0.07008022 %I 6.9105678E-5 - 9.4757886 ] . [ 1.2604034 %I - 0.0237679875 ] ) TERM1)
      [                               ]
      [ 8.0106107 - 7.4505806E-9 %I ]

```

Figure 4.2.1 (iii) Example of numerical calculation.

```

[ 0.020214025 ]
[ ]
0.27617158 CONTIN ((3.1506453E-11 %I - 0.031771524) (t0, 1.5, 0.2) . [ - 1.23709832 %I ])
[ ]
[ - 5.0072172 ]

([ - 0.07008022 %I 6.9105678E-5 - 9.4757886 ] . 0.55234316 (t0, 1.5, 0.2)) TERM2
[ 1.5480223 %I + 0.0193519525 ]
[ ]
- 0.01266222726 (t0, 1.5, 0.2) . [ 1.2604034 %I - 0.0237679875 ])
[ ]
[ 8.0106107 - 7.4505806E-9 %I ]

([ - 0.07008022 %I 6.9105678E-5 - 9.4757886 ] . 0.55234316 (t0, 1.5, 0.2)) TERM1)

[ 0.020214025 ]
[ ]
0.27617158 FLOWCUR ((3.1506453E-11 %I - 0.031771524) (t0, 1.5, 0.2) . [ - 1.23709832 %I ])
[ ]
[ - 5.0072172 ]

[ 1.5480223 %I + 0.0193519525 ]
[ ]
TERM2 - 0.01266222726 (t0, 1.5, 0.2) . [ 1.2604034 %I - 0.0237679875 ]) TERM1)
[ ]
[ 8.0106107 - 7.4505806E-9 %I ]

3.49694735E-3 (3.1506453E-11 %I - 0.031771524)
([ - 0.07008022 %I 6.9105678E-5 - 9.4757886 ] . (t0, 1.5, 0.2)) PRESSURE

TIME= 2733 MSEC.

(C32) DOALLMXOPS:TRUE$
TIME= 4 MSEC.

(C33) MEL:EV(MEL,DOTSCRULES=TRUE,EXPAND);
TIME= 5024 MSEC.
(D33) 0.016282179 %I FLOWCUR TERM2 + 8.7870575E-3 FLOWCUR TERM2 + 0.01349317212 %I CONVEC TERM2
+ 4.78828E-3 CONVEC TERM2 - 0.017042885 %I CONTIN TERM2 - 9.19759023E-3 CONTIN TERM2
- 6.6113465E-3 %I FLOWCUR TERM1 - 5.4778637E-3 FLOWCUR TERM1 + 0.02115748776 %I CONVEC TERM1
+ 7.0866198E-3 CONVEC TERM1 + 6.9202297E-3 %I CONTIN TERM1 + 5.7337903E-3 CONTIN TERM1
- 2.08790246E-13 %I PRESSURE + 2.1054685E-4 PRESSURE

(C34) MEL:EV(MEL,TERM1=1,TERM2=1);
TIME= 293 MSEC.
(D34) - 2.08790246E-13 %I PRESSURE + 2.1054685E-4 PRESSURE + 9.6708324E-3 %I FLOWCUR
+ 3.3091938E-3 FLOWCUR + 0.03465066 %I CONVEC + 0.01187489985 CONVEC - 0.010122655 %I CONTIN
- 3.46379983E-3 CONTIN

```

Figure 4.2.1 (iv) Example of numerical calculation.

```

(C35) MEL:EV(MEL,CONVEC=1,FLOWCUR=1,PRESSURE=1,CONTIN=1);
TIME= 126 MSEC.
(D35)                                0.034198838 %I + 0.0119308408

(C36) LOADFILE(SIG,COLD,DSK,PLASMA)$

SIG COLD DSK PLASMA BEING LOADED
LOADING DONE
TIME= 484 MSEC.

(C37) (UN[C]:1,UN[P]:UN[P1])$
TIME= 23 MSEC.

(C38) SIG:EV(SIGMAN[II])$
TIME= 11 MSEC.

(C39) KILL(SIGMAN)$
TIME= 5 MSEC.

(C40) SIGMAN[II]:='SIG$
TIME= 10 MSEC.

(C41) KILL(SIG)$
TIME= 6 MSEC.

(C42) VI[K]:=EV(SIGMAN[K].KN[K],EVAL,EXPAND)$
TIME= 15 MSEC.

(C43) NI[K]:=EV(KN[K].(VI[K]/UN[K]),EVAL,EXPAND)$
TIME= 29 MSEC.

(C44) VIT[K]:=EV(KN[K].SIGMAN[K],EVAL,EXPAND)$
TIME= 16 MSEC.

(C45) DISPLAY(VI[A],VI[B],NI[A],NI[B],VIT[N])$

(ROW TO COL CONVERSION MADE)
                                [ 0.040755402 ]
                                [           ]
(E46) VI = [ - 1.3585134E-3 %I ]
           A [           ]
           [ 2.69314113E-3 ]

(ROW TO COL CONVERSION MADE)
                                [ 1.89000268E-3 %I + 0.043379309 ]
                                [           ]
(E47) VI = [ 1.53884464E-3 %I - 0.053278289 ]
           B [           ]
           [ - 4.2287245E-3 ]

(E48) NI = 1.66641024E-3
           A

(E49) NI = 4.7322825E-3
           B

```

Figure 4.2.1 (v) Example of numerical calculation.

```

(E50)          VIT = [ - 0.65853108 %I  1.1922499  0.110468633 ]
                N
TIME= 2232 MSEC.

(C51) DOALLMXOPS:FALSE$
TIME= 4 MSEC.

(C52) MION:EV(MION,EVAL)$
TIME= 815 MSEC.

(C53) DISPTERMS(MION)$

+
[ 1.89000268E-3 %I + 0.043379309 ]
[ ]
- 0.27617158 CONVEC (([1.22130355, 0, 0.080794234] . [ 1.53884464E-3 %I - 0.053278289 ]))
[ ]
[ - 4.2287245E-3 ]

[ 0.040755402 ]
[ ]
([ - 0.65853108 %I  1.1922499  0.110468633 ] . [ - 1.3585134E-3 %I ]) TERM2
[ ]
[ 2.69314113E-3 ]

[ 0.040755402 ]
[ ]
+ ([- 1.22130355, 1.5, 0.119205762] . [ - 1.3585134E-3 %I ])
[ ]
[ 2.69314113E-3 ]

[ 1.89000268E-3 %I + 0.043379309 ]
[ ]
([ - 0.65853108 %I  1.1922499  0.110468633 ] . [ 1.53884464E-3 %I - 0.053278289 ] ) TERM1)
[ ]
[ - 4.2287245E-3 ]

[ 0.040755402 ]
[ ]
- 0.27617158 FLOWCUR (4.7322825E-3 ([0, 1.5, 0.2] . [ - 1.3585134E-3 %I ]) TERM2
[ ]
[ 2.69314113E-3 ]

[ 1.89000268E-3 %I + 0.043379309 ]
[ ]
+ 1.66641024E-3 ([0, 1.5, 0.2] . [ 1.53884464E-3 %I - 0.053278289 ] ) TERM1)
[ ]
[ - 4.2287245E-3 ]

TIME= 1608 MSEC.

(C54) DOALLMXOPS:TRUE$
TIME= 4 MSEC.

```

Figure 4.2.1 (vi) Example of numerical calculation.

(C55) MION:EV(MION,DOTSCRULES=TRUE,EXPAND);

TIME= 4383 MSEC.

(D55) $2.6632065E-6$ %I FLOWCUR TERM2 - $7.0394506E-7$ FLOWCUR TERM2 + $4.1351055E-4$ %I CONVEC TERM2

- $2.2466464E-5$ CONVEC TERM2 - $1.06229943E-6$ %I FLOWCUR TERM1 + $3.7168439E-5$ FLOWCUR TERM1

- $4.0040724E-4$ %I CONVEC TERM1 - $8.4188862E-4$ CONVEC TERM1

(C56) MION:EV(MION,TERM1=1,TERM2=1);

TIME= 163 MSEC.

(D56) $1.6009071E-6$ %I FLOWCUR + $3.6464494E-5$ FLOWCUR + $1.3103312E-5$ %I CONVEC

- $8.64355075E-4$ CONVEC

(C57) MION:EV(MION,CONVEC=1,FLOWCUR=1);

TIME= 67 MSEC.

(D57) $1.47042192E-5$ %I - $8.27890574E-4$

(C58) MION+MEL;

TIME= 11 MSEC.

(D58) 0.034213542 %I + 0.0111029502

Figure 4.2.1 (vii) Example of numerical calculation.

C31). The matrix multiplications are carried out by resetting DOALLMXOPS to TRUE (C32), and re-evaluating MEL (C33); DOTSCRULES is set to TRUE in this step, so that the $VET[N] \cdot (KN[N]/WN[N])$ term, which contains scalars and vectors, in the continuity part of MEL is correctly treated. In C34 and C35 we substitute 1 for the dummy variables TERM1, CONVEC etc. and recover the numerical result for MEL. An identical set of steps accomplishes the same result for MION (C36 - C57). Finally MION and MEL are summed to give MTOT (C58).

By running the program just described for various values of frequency and wave number, we can build up a feeling for the effect of each nonlinear term. Figures 2 - 4 summarize some typical results for coupling to ion acoustic, electrostatic ion cyclotron and magnetosonic waves, respectively. For the case of coupling to ion acoustic waves (figure 2, α and β are defined in figure 3.4.2(a)), we see that the largest terms are the electron continuity and flowcurrent. However in every case a cancellation occurs that reduces the effect of these terms by about three orders of magnitude. Furthermore a cancellation occurs between the sum of the flowcurrent and continuity terms and the electron convective term. So the electron pressure term, which is smaller than any other electron term, would seem to give the best approximation to the total electron part of the coupling coefficient. Turning our attention to the ion terms, we see that again there are considerable cancellations occurring, and that as a consequence the total for the ions is about a factor of 30 less than either of the individual terms. Comparing the electron and ion terms, we see that the ion term is generally larger by about a factor of about 5. So for coupling to these waves the dominant nonlinearities are the two ion terms; but an analytic calculation of the coupling coefficient, based on this information would have to be accurate enough to give some finite answer after the cancellation occurs.

α	$\pi/3$	$\pi/3$	$\pi/6$
β	0	$\pi/6$	$\pi/3$
convective	- 0.0004707	- 0.0005426 - i 0.0001681	- 0.0005593 - i 0.0005232
continuity	0.2236034	0.1942757 + i 0.0602428	0.1964797 + i 0.1838595
flowcurrent	- 0.2230917	- 0.1936861 - i 0.0600600	- 0.1958939 - i 0.1833113
pressure	- 0.0001621	- 0.0001623	- 0.0001623
electron term	- 0.0001211	- 0.0001154 + i 0.0000146	- 0.0001359 + i 0.0000249
convective	0.0223368	0.0223798 - i 0.0009187	0.0119057 - i 0.0024062
flowcurrent	- 0.0215879	- 0.0216548 + i 0.0006197	- 0.0127104 + i 0.0018904
ion term	0.0007488	0.0007250 - i 0.0002989	- 0.0007246 - i 0.0005157
total	0.0006277	0.0006096 - i 0.0002843	- 0.0008605 - i 0.0004907

$$KN\Gamma A1 = [0.5, 0, 5E-3]$$

Figure 4.2.2 Numerical results for coupling to ion acoustic waves.

KNX [N]	1.4	1.0	0
KNY [N]	0	1.0	1.4
convective	0.0096641	0.0107372 + i 0.0307297	0.0105943 + i 0.0290569
continuity	0.0059726	0.0360608 + i 0.1031916	- 0.0449321 - i 0.1232463
flowcurrent	- 0.0057297	- 0.0360543 - i 0.1031730	0.0449239 + i 0.1232239
pressure	0.0001333	0.0001815	0.0001757
electron term	0.0100404	0.0109252 + i 0.0307483	0.0107619 + i 0.0290344
convective	- 0.0011525	- 0.0004051 - i 0.0001080	- 0.0012347 - i 0.0001382
flowcurrent	- 0.0000938	- 0.0003387 - i 0.0000147	0.0004474 + i 0.0000177
ion term	- 0.0012464	- 0.0007438 - i 0.0001228	- 0.0007873 - i 0.0001205
total	0.0087840	0.0101814 + i 0.0306255	0.0099745 + i 0.0289139

$$WNFA1 = 30. \quad KNZFN1 = 0.2$$

Figure 4.2.3 Numerical results for coupling to electrostatic ion cyclotron waves.

KNX [N]	0.2	0.14	0
KNY [N]	0	0.14	0.2

convective	0.0112812	0.0113064 + i 0.0038577	0.0113288 + i 0.0052577
continuity	0.0086338	0.0057846 + i 0.0019736	- 0.0005062 - i 0.0002350
flowcurrent	- 0.0086291	- 0.0057815 - i 0.0019726	0.0005059 + i 0.0002349
pressure	0.0001915	0.0001925	0.0001933

electron term	0.0114775	0.0115021 + i 0.0038588	0.0115219 + i 0.0052576

convective	- 0.0010888	- 0.0011325 - i 0.0000233	- 0.0012280 - i 0.0000322
flowcurrent	- 0.0001303	- 0.0000866 - i 0.0000002	0.0000084 + i 0.0000001

ion term	- 0.0012192	- 0.0012192 - i 0.0000236	- 0.0012195 - i 0.0000322

total	0.0102582	0.0102828 + i 0.0038351	0.0103023 + i 0.0052253

$$WNFA1 = 30. \quad KNZFN1 = 0.2$$

Figure 4.2.4 Numerical results for coupling to magnetosonic waves.

For coupling to an electrostatic ion cyclotron wave (figure 3), we again see a cancellation occurring between the electron flowcurrent and continuity terms, turning what are in some cases the largest terms into something that makes a negligible contribution to the total for the electrons. Thus, since the pressure term is small, the convective term is the dominant contribution to the electron term. For the ions the convective term is about an order of magnitude greater than the flowcurrent; and the total for the ions is, in turn, an order of magnitude smaller than the electron term. So for this interaction, the dominant nonlinearity is the electron convective one. We find a similar picture for coupling to magnetosonic waves (figure 4), with the electron convective term again dominating the interaction.

4.3 Coupling to Ion Acoustic Waves

We now come to the derivation of an approximate *analytic* expression for the coupling coefficient for excitation of ion acoustic waves by a pump at the lower hybrid frequency. First of all we will outline a very rough scheme, by which we can order the various nonlinearities, as this will give us some feeling for what to expect when we come to the work with TAYLOR on MACSYMA (see section 4.1).

In this scheme, since $\Omega_e \gg \omega \gg \Omega_i$ for all three modes participating in the interaction, we will assume that the induced electron orbits are correctly given by taking $B_0 \rightarrow \infty$, and that the induced ion orbits by $B_0 \rightarrow 0$. In addition, we will assume that the electron orbits induced by the lower hybrid mode are essentially as if the electrons were cold (i.e. $v_{te} \rightarrow 0$), and that the electron orbits induced by the ion acoustic modes are dominated by a pressure force (i.e. $\omega/k_z \ll v_{te}$). Note that these are the same limits that we have already made in obtaining the dispersion

relations for these modes (section 3.2); their significance is discussed in section 3.3.

Having made these approximations, it is still necessary to find the large and small parameters in the problem, so that the various terms can be compared. By tracing the course of the numerical calculations, it is possible to discover these parameters. For this problem they are $m_i/m_e \equiv \mu$, which is of course large, and $k_a c_s/\omega_a \equiv \epsilon_1$ and $\cos \theta_a \equiv \epsilon_2$, both of which are small. (a is the pump, a lower hybrid mode.) Using this information we may evaluate the velocities and densities (equations 2.4.21 and 2.4.22) of the pump and idler keeping only these large and small factors. We find:

$$v_{ai} \sim \epsilon_1 \quad (1)$$

$$n_{ai} \sim \epsilon_1^2 \quad (2)$$

$$v_{ae} \sim \mu \epsilon_1 \epsilon_2 \quad (3)$$

$$n_{ae} \sim \mu \epsilon_1^2 \epsilon_2^2 \quad (4)$$

$$v_{bi} \sim v_{be} \sim 1 \quad (5)$$

$$n_{bi} \sim n_{be} \sim 1 \quad (6)$$

(As we saw in section 3.3, v_e is parallel to the z axis, and that v_i is parallel to k .) Substituting these into our expression for the coupling coefficient (equations 2.3.14 and 2.4.46), we find the nonlinearities vary thus:

$$\text{electron convective} \sim \epsilon_1 \epsilon_2 \quad (7)$$

$$\text{electron continuity} \sim \mu \epsilon_1 \epsilon_2 \quad (8)$$

$$\text{electron flowcurrent} \sim \mu \epsilon_1 \epsilon_2 \quad (9)$$

$$\text{electron pressure} \sim \mu \epsilon_1^2 \epsilon_2^2 \quad (10)$$

$$\text{ion convective} \sim \epsilon_1 \quad (11)$$

$$\text{ion flowcurrent} \sim \epsilon_1 \quad (12)$$

We see that indeed the terms we saw approximately cancelling numerically in section

4.2, are of the same order, although at this stage, we cannot see the cancellations analytically, nor can we know the result of the cancellations.

In order to take this analysis further, we must carry out the calculation keeping higher order terms in our small parameters. We will also need to introduce small parameters involving the magnetic field. We shall do all the expansions in these small parameters using TAYLOR (see section 4.1). Before we do this however, we must find some way of comparing various powers of the small parameters, so that we can know which terms to drop. Now TAYLOR only works when making expansions in a single parameter. So in order to handle more than one small parameter we express all of them in terms of a single small parameter. At the same time we can also give MACSYMA information about their relative magnitudes. So we shall express the parameters already introduced as follows:

$$\mu = 1/\delta^2 \quad (13)$$

$$\epsilon_1 = \lambda_1 \delta \quad (14)$$

$$\epsilon_2 = \lambda_2 \delta \quad (15)$$

where λ_1 and $\lambda_2 \sim 1$. We may then proceed to make a Taylor series in δ about zero. Note that by regulating the powers of δ in equations 13 to 15 we are able to govern how TAYLOR truncates the series. At the end we need only substitute for δ , λ_1 and λ_2 to recover the original parameters μ , ϵ_1 and ϵ_2 . The terms in the final series in δ will contain polynomials in the λ 's. Unless the λ 's are all close to unity, there is a chance that these coefficients will be of order δ . It is therefore a good idea to try and keep enough orders in δ to have two significant terms left in the answer. Of course at the outset how many this should be might not be known and so the truncation levels might have to be reset after an initial run. Remember a final check can always be made against the exact numerical calculation.

In addition to the parameters given in equations 13, 14 and 15 we shall use the following parameters involving the magnetic field:

$$\Omega_i/\omega_a \equiv \epsilon_3 = \lambda_3 \delta \quad (16)$$

$$\omega_a/\Omega_e \equiv \epsilon_4 = \lambda_4 \delta^2 \quad (17)$$

We chose this ordering because it reflects the fact that ϵ_4 is considerably smaller than ϵ_3 . However note that from equation 13 we find that $\lambda_3 \lambda_4 = \delta^{-1}$. We give the information of equations 1 to 5 to MACSYMA with the following assignments:

$$\text{MU} : 1 / \text{DTA}\uparrow 2 \quad (18)$$

$$\text{KNX}[A] : \text{LM1} * \text{DTA} * \text{WN}[A] \quad (19)$$

$$\text{KNZ}[A] : \text{LM1} * \text{LM2} * \text{DTA}\uparrow 2 * \text{WN}[A] \quad (20)$$

$$\text{WN}[C1] : \text{LM3} * \text{DTA} * \text{WN}[A] \quad (21)$$

$$\text{WN}[CE] : \text{WN}[A] / \text{DTA}\uparrow 2 / \text{LM4} \quad (22)$$

Note that in these statements we have expressed frequencies and wave numbers in terms of $\text{WN}[A]$. TAYLOR will in effect assume undefined frequencies and wave numbers are of the same order as $\text{WN}[A]$.

Figure 1 shows the other commands involved in getting the ion term of the coupling coefficient. We shall describe these in some detail, and content ourselves with quoting the results for the electrons. The rough structure of the calculation here, is similar to that for the numerical calculation, described in section 4.2. We shall state here that we try and do all the initial calculations keeping 3 significant terms in the Taylor series. Near the end the leading terms will cancel (as we noted in section 4.2), leaving us with 2 significant terms. Since the final answer is of order $\text{DTA}\uparrow 2$, the level of truncation on the various parts of the coupling coefficient should be 3.

In line C1 we set some MACSYMA switches that govern the representation in

(C1) (EZGCDSWITCH:FALSE,RATMX:FALSE,POWERDISP:TRUE,DOALLMXOPS:TRUE,TIME:TRUE,LINEL:95,
DOTASSOC:FALSE,NOLABELS:TRUE)\$

TIME= 34 MSEC.

(C2) RATVARS (KNZ[A],KNM[A],WN[B],WN[N],WN[A],LM4,LM3,LM2,LM1,MU,DTA)\$
TIME= 127 MSEC.

(C3) (KNX[A]:DTA*WN[A]*LM1,KNY[A]:0,KNZ[A]:KNX[A]*LM2*DTA,MU:1/DTA²,
WN[C1]:LM3*DTA*WN[A],WN[C2]:WN[A]/DTA²/LM4)\$
TIME= 183 MSEC.

(C4) (TAY(X,P):=TAYLOR(EV(X),DTA,0,P),KN[I]:=[KNX[I],KNY[I],KNZ[I]])\$
TIME= 28 MSEC.

(C5) LOADFILE (SYMCC,ION,DSK,PLASMA)\$

SYMCC ION DSK PLASMA BEING LOADED

LOADING DONE

TIME= 345 MSEC.

(C6) DISPLAY (WN[A],WN[N],WN[B],KN[A],KN[N],KN[B])\$

(E7)
$$\begin{matrix} \text{WN} & = & \text{WN} \\ \text{A} & & \text{A} \end{matrix}$$

(E8)
$$\begin{matrix} \text{WN} & = & \text{WN} \\ \text{N} & & \text{N} \end{matrix}$$

(E9)
$$\begin{matrix} \text{WN} & = & \text{WN} \\ \text{B} & & \text{B} \end{matrix}$$

(E10)
$$\text{KN} = \left[\begin{matrix} \text{WN} & \text{DTA} & \text{LM1} & , & 0 & , & \text{WN} & \text{DTA} & \text{LM1} & \text{LM2} \\ \text{A} & & \text{A} & & & & \text{A} & & & \end{matrix} \right]^2$$

(E11)
$$\text{KN} = \left[\begin{matrix} \text{KNX} & , & \text{KNY} & , & \text{KNZ} \\ \text{N} & & \text{N} & & \text{N} \end{matrix} \right]$$

(E12)
$$\text{KN} = \left[\begin{matrix} \text{KNX} & , & \text{KNY} & , & \text{KNZ} \\ \text{B} & & \text{B} & & \text{B} \end{matrix} \right]$$

TIME= 153 MSEC.

(C13) DISPLAY (MICONV,MIFLOW)\$

(E14)
$$\text{MICONV} = \frac{\begin{matrix} (\text{KN} & . & \text{VI}) & (\text{VIT} & . & \text{VI}) & + & (\text{KN} & . & \text{VI}) & (\text{VIT} & . & \text{VI}) \\ \text{A} & & \text{B} & & \text{N} & & \text{A} & & \text{B} & & \text{A} & & \text{N} & & \text{B} \end{matrix}}{2 \text{WN}} \frac{\text{N}}{\text{N}}$$

(E15)
$$\text{MIFLOW} = \frac{\begin{matrix} \text{NI} & (\text{KN} & . & \text{VI}) & + & \text{NI} & (\text{KN} & . & \text{VI}) \\ \text{B} & & \text{N} & & \text{A} & & \text{A} & & \text{N} & & \text{B} \end{matrix}}{2 \text{WN}} \frac{\text{N}}{\text{N}}$$

TIME= 15 MSEC.

Figure 4.3.1 (i) Solution by Taylor series method

(C16) LOADFILE (SIG,COLD,DSK,PLASMA)\$

SIG COLD DSK PLASMA BEING LOADED
 LOADING DONE
 TIME= 521 MSEC.

(C17) (WN[C]:WN[CII],WN[P]:WN[PII])\$
 TIME= 26 MSEC.

(C18) SIG: MATRIXMAP (RATSIMP, EV (SIGMAN [I], EVAL))\$
 TIME= 9569 MSEC.

(C19) KILL (SIGMAN)\$
 TIME= 6 MSEC.

(C20) SIGMAN [K] := TAY (EV (SIG, I=K, EVAL), 2)\$
 TIME= 14 MSEC.

(C21) BLOCK (DISPLAY (SIGMAN [A]), DISPLAY (SIGMAN [B]), DISPLAY (SIGMAN [N]),
 SIGMAN [A] : MATRIXMAP (LAMBDA ([CC], TAYLOR (CC, DTA, 0, 3)), SIGMAN [A]),
 VI [A] : SIGMAN [A] . KN [A], DISPLAY (VI [A]),
 VI [B] : SIGMAN [B] . KN [B], DISPLAY (VI [B]), VI [B] : TAY (VI [B], 3),
 NI [A] : (KN [A] . VI [A]) / WN [A], DISPLAY (NI [A]),
 NI [B] : (KN [B] . VI [B]) / WN [B], DISPLAY (NI [B]), NI [B] : TAY (NI [B], 3),
 VIT [N] : KN [N] . SIGMAN [N], DISPLAY (VIT [N]), VIT [N] : TAY (VIT [N], 3))\$

NPOWER FASL DSK MACSYM BEING LOADED
 LOADING DONE

NRATS FASL DSK MACSYM BEING LOADED
 LOADING DONE

1205 MSEC.
 (MACSYMA-BREAK)
 +LINENUM;
 21
 +EXIT;
 EXITED FROM THE BREAK

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left[\begin{array}{c} 1 \\ \frac{1}{WN} \\ \frac{1}{A} \end{array} \right] \left[\begin{array}{c} LM3 \ DTA^2 \\ \frac{LM3 \ DTA^2}{WN} \\ \frac{LM3 \ DTA^2}{A} \end{array} \right] + \dots \\
 (E22) /R/ \quad \text{SIGMAN} &= \left[\begin{array}{c} \frac{1}{WN} \\ \frac{1}{A} \end{array} \right] \left[\begin{array}{c} LM3 \ DTA \\ \frac{LM3 \ DTA}{WN} \\ \frac{LM3 \ DTA}{A} \end{array} \right] + \dots \\
 & \left[\begin{array}{c} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{array} \right] \left[\begin{array}{c} 1 \\ 0 \\ 0 \end{array} \right] \left[\begin{array}{c} 1 \\ WN \\ A \end{array} \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 4.3.1 (ii) Solution by Taylor series method

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \left[\begin{array}{c} 1 \\ \frac{WN}{B} + \frac{WN^2 LM3 DTA^2}{A^3} + \dots \\ \frac{WN^2 LM3 \%I DTA}{A^3} \\ 0 \end{array} \right] \\
 (E23)/R/ \text{ SIGMAN } & = \left[\begin{array}{c} \frac{WN^2 LM3 \%I DTA}{A^3} \\ \frac{1}{WN} + \frac{WN^2 LM3 DTA^2}{B^3} + \dots \\ \frac{WN^2}{B^2} \\ 0 \end{array} \right] \\
 & \left[\begin{array}{c} 1 \\ \frac{WN}{N} + \frac{WN^2 LM3 DTA^2}{N^3} + \dots \\ \frac{WN^2 LM3 \%I DTA}{A^3} \\ 0 \end{array} \right] \\
 (E24)/R/ \text{ SIGMAN } & = \left[\begin{array}{c} \frac{WN^2 LM3 \%I DTA}{A^3} \\ \frac{1}{WN} + \frac{WN^2 LM3 DTA^2}{B^3} + \dots \\ \frac{WN^2}{B^2} \\ 0 \end{array} \right] \\
 & \left[\begin{array}{c} 1 \\ \frac{WN}{N} + \frac{WN^2 LM3 DTA^2}{N^3} + \dots \\ \frac{WN^2 LM3 \%I DTA}{A^3} \\ 0 \end{array} \right] \\
 (ROW TO COL CONVERSION MADE) & \\
 (E25)/R/ \text{ VI } & = \left[\begin{array}{c} \frac{LM1 DTA + \frac{WN^2}{A}}{\text{Sqrt}(WN)} \\ - \%I LM1 LM3 DTA^2 \\ LM1 LM2 DTA^2 \end{array} \right]
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 4.3.1 (iii) Solution by Taylor series method

$$\begin{aligned}
 &+ \text{KNY} \left(\text{LM1 LM3} \left(\text{WN}^2 \text{KNX} \text{KNY} \text{WN}^3 - \text{WN}^2 \text{KNX} \text{KNY} \text{WN}^3 + \text{WN} \text{KNX} \text{KNY} \text{WN}^2 \text{WN}^3 \right) \right. \\
 &+ \text{LM3} \left(- \text{ZI} \text{WN}^2 \text{KNX} \text{WN}^2 \text{LM1} \text{WN}^3 - \text{ZI} \text{WN}^2 \text{KNX} \text{KNZ} \text{WN} \text{LM1 LM2} \text{WN}^3 \right) \\
 &+ \text{KNX} \left(\text{WN}^2 \text{KNZ} \text{WN}^2 \text{LM1 LM2} \text{WN}^3 + \text{LM1 LM3} \left(\text{WN}^2 \text{KNX} \text{WN}^2 \text{WN}^3 + \text{WN}^2 \text{KNY} \text{WN}^2 \text{WN}^3 \right) \right. \\
 &+ \text{WN} \text{KNX} \text{WN}^2 \text{WN}^3 \left. \right) + \text{LM3} \left(\text{ZI} \text{WN}^3 \text{KNY} \text{WN}^2 \text{LM1} \text{WN}^3 + \text{ZI} \text{WN}^2 \text{KNY} \text{KNZ} \text{WN} \text{LM1 LM2} \right. \\
 &\left. \text{WN}^3 \right) \left. \right) / \left(2 \text{WN}^3 \text{WN}^3 \text{WN}^6 \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

TIME= 17942 MSEC.

(C35) DISPTERMS(MIFLOW)\$

+

$$\begin{aligned}
 &\left(\text{KNX}^2 + \text{KNY}^2 + \text{KNZ}^2 \right) \text{DTA LM1 KNX} \\
 &\text{-----} \\
 &\quad \quad \quad \text{2 WN}^2 \text{WN} \\
 &\quad \quad \quad \text{B} \quad \quad \text{N} \\
 &\left(\text{DTA} \left(\left(- \text{ZI} \text{WN}^2 \text{KNY} \text{WN}^2 \text{LM1 LM3} + \left(- \text{WN}^3 \text{KNX}^2 - \text{WN}^3 \text{KNY}^2 \right) \right) \right. \right. \\
 &+ \left(- \text{WN} \text{KNX}^2 - \text{WN} \text{KNY}^2 - \text{WN} \text{KNZ}^2 \right) \text{WN}^2 \left. \right) \text{LM1 LM3} \left. \right) \text{KNX} + \text{ZI} \text{WN}^2 \text{KNX} \text{WN}^2 \text{LM1 LM3} \\
 &\left. \right) \left. \right) / \left(2 \text{WN}^4 \text{WN}^4 \text{WN}^4 \right) \\
 &- \left(\text{DTA} \left(\text{KNX} \text{WN}^2 \text{LM1} \text{KNX} + \left(\text{KNY} \text{WN}^2 \text{LM1} + \left(- \text{ZI} \text{KNX}^2 - \text{ZI} \text{KNY}^2 - \text{ZI} \text{KNZ}^2 \right) \text{LM1 LM3} \right) \right. \right. \\
 &\quad \quad \quad \text{KNY} + \left(\text{KNZ} \text{WN}^2 \text{LM1} + \left(\text{KNX}^2 + \text{KNY}^2 + \text{KNZ}^2 \right) \text{LM1 LM2} \right) \text{KNZ} \left. \right) \left. \right) / \left(2 \text{WN}^2 \text{WN}^2 \right)
 \end{aligned}$$

TIME= 6586 MSEC.

Figure 4.3.1 (vi) Solution by Taylor series method

(C36) (TRIGRED(X)):=SUBST((COS(ALP)↑2=1-SIN(ALP)↑2,COS(ALP)↑3=COS(ALP)*(1-SIN(ALP)↑2),
 COS(ALP)↑4=(1-SIN(ALP)↑2)↑2,COS(BET)↑2=1-SIN(BET)↑2,COS(BET)↑3=COS(BET)*(1-SIN(BET)↑2),
 COS(BET)↑4=(1-SIN(BET)↑2)↑2),X),KN[I]:=[KNX[I],KNY[I],KNZ[I]])\$
 TIME= 300 MSEC.

(C37) LOADFILE(IARSCN,TAY,DSK,CFK)\$

IARSCN TAY DSK CFK BEING LOADED
 LOADING DONE
 TIME= 1059 MSEC.

(C38) DISPLAY(WN[A],WN[N],WN[B],KN[A],KN[N],KN[B])\$

(E39)

$$\frac{WN}{A} = \frac{WN}{A}$$

(E40)/R/

$$\frac{WN}{N} = \frac{WN}{2} + \frac{WN \cdot LM1 \cdot \sin(\alpha) \cdot DTA}{2} + \dots$$

(E41)/R/

$$\frac{WN}{B} = \frac{WN}{2} + \frac{WN \cdot LM1 \cdot \sin(\alpha) \cdot DTA}{2} + \dots$$

(E42)

$$KN = [\frac{WN \cdot LM1 \cdot DTA}{A}, 0, \frac{WN \cdot LM1 \cdot LM2 \cdot DTA^2}{A}]$$

(E43)/R/

$$KN_N = [\frac{WN \cdot \sin(\alpha)}{2} + \frac{(-\cos(\beta) \cos(\alpha) \cdot LM2 \cdot WN + WN \cdot LM1) \cdot DTA}{2} + \dots, \frac{((- LM2 \cdot \frac{WN^2}{A} - \frac{WN^2 \cdot LM1}{A}) \sin(\alpha) + \frac{WN^2 \cdot LM1 \cdot \sin^3(\alpha)}{A}) \cdot DTA}{4} + \dots, \frac{\sin(\beta) \cos(\alpha) \cdot \frac{WN^2}{A} \cdot (-1 + \sin^2(\alpha)) \cdot LM1 \cdot \sin(\beta) \cos(\alpha) \cdot \frac{WN \cdot DTA^2}{A}}{2} + \frac{\sin(\beta) \cos(\alpha) \cdot \frac{WN^2}{A} \cdot (-1 + \sin^2(\alpha)) \cdot LM1 \cdot \sin(\beta) \cos(\alpha) \cdot \frac{WN \cdot DTA^2}{A}}{4} + \dots, \frac{\cos(\beta) \cos(\alpha) \cdot \frac{WN}{A} \cdot LM2 \cdot \frac{WN \cdot \sin(\alpha) \cdot DTA}{A}}{2} + \frac{((- \cos(\beta) \cos(\alpha) \cdot LM2 \cdot \frac{WN^2}{A} + 2 \cdot LM2 \cdot \frac{WN \cdot LM1}{A} - \cos(\beta) \cos(\alpha) \cdot \frac{WN^2}{A} \cdot LM1^2 + \cos(\beta) \cos(\alpha) \cdot \frac{WN^2 \cdot LM1 \cdot \sin^2(\alpha)}{A}) \cdot DTA)}{4} + \dots]$$

Figure 4.3.1 (vii) Solution by Taylor series method

$$\begin{aligned}
 (E44)/R/ \quad KN_B &= \left[\frac{WN \sin(\alpha) (\cos(\beta) \cos(\alpha) LM_2 WN + WN LM_1) DTA}{A^2} \right. \\
 &+ \frac{((-LM_2^2 \frac{WN}{A} - WN LM_1^2) \sin(\alpha) + WN LM_1^2 \sin^3(\alpha)) DTA}{A^4} + \dots, \\
 &\frac{\sin(\beta) \cos(\alpha) \frac{WN}{A} (-1 + \sin^2(\alpha)) LM_1^2 \sin(\beta) \cos(\alpha) \frac{WN}{A} DTA}{A^4} + \dots, \\
 &\frac{\cos(\beta) \cos(\alpha) \frac{WN}{A} LM_2 \frac{WN}{A} \sin(\alpha) DTA}{A^2} + \frac{((- \cos(\beta) \cos(\alpha) LM_2^2 \frac{WN}{A} - 2 LM_2 \frac{WN}{A} LM_1}{A})}{A^2} \\
 &\left. - \cos(\beta) \cos(\alpha) \frac{WN}{A} LM_1^2 + \cos(\beta) \cos(\alpha) \frac{WN}{A} LM_1^2 \sin^2(\alpha) DTA \right) / 4 + \dots]
 \end{aligned}$$

TIME= 146 MSEC.

```

(C45) BLOCK (KNX[B]:TAY(KNX[B],3),KNX[N]:TAY(KNX[N],3),KNY[B]:TAY(KNY[B],3),
KNY[N]:TAY(KNY[N],3),KNZ[B]:TAY(KNZ[B],3),KNZ[N]:TAY(KNZ[N],3),WN[B]:TAY(WN[B],3),
WN[N]:TAY(WN[N],3))$
TIME= 18102 MSEC.

```

```

(C46) MICONV:TRIGRED(EV(MICONV,EVAL));
TIME= 416479 MSEC.

```

$$\begin{aligned}
 (D46)/R/ \quad &(2 \sin(\alpha) LM_1 DTA + (-2 \%I \cos(\alpha) \sin(\beta) LM_3 LM_1 + (-2 + 2 \sin^2(\alpha)) LM_1^2) \\
 &DTA + (((2 \sin(\alpha) + 8 \sin^3(\alpha) + (8 \sin(\alpha) - 8 \sin^3(\alpha)) \sin(\beta)) LM_3^2 \\
 &+ \sin(\alpha) LM_2^2) LM_1 - 18 \%I \cos(\alpha) \sin(\alpha) \sin(\beta) LM_3 LM_1^2 \\
 &+ (-3 \sin(\alpha) + 3 \sin^3(\alpha)) LM_1^3) DTA) / 4
 \end{aligned}$$

```

(C47) MIFLOW:TRIGRED(EV(MIFLOW,EVAL));
TIME= 246079 MSEC.

```

$$\begin{aligned}
 (D47)/R/ \quad &-(2 \sin(\alpha) LM_1 DTA + (-2 \%I \cos(\alpha) \sin(\beta) LM_3 LM_1 - 2 \sin^2(\alpha) LM_1^2) DTA \\
 &+ (((2 \sin(\alpha) + 8 \sin^3(\alpha) + (8 \sin(\alpha) - 8 \sin^3(\alpha)) \sin(\beta)) LM_3^2 + \sin(\alpha) LM_2^2) \\
 &LM_1 + 2 \%I \cos(\alpha) \sin(\alpha) \sin(\beta) LM_3 LM_1^2 + (-3 \sin(\alpha) + 3 \sin^3(\alpha)) LM_1^3) DTA) / 4
 \end{aligned}$$

Figure 4.3.1 (viii) Solution by Taylor series method

(C48) MION:MIFLOW+MICONV;
TIME= 228 MSEC.

$$(D48)/R/ \quad \frac{(1 - 2 \sin^2(\alpha)) \text{LM1}^2 \text{DTA}^2 + 10 \cos(\alpha) \sin(\alpha) \sin(\beta) \text{LM3} \text{LM1}^2 \text{DTA}^3}{2}$$

(C49) KILL (ARRAYS)\$
TIME= 17 MSEC.

(C50) (DTA:1/SQRT(MU),LM1:KNM[A]*SQRT(MU)/WN[A],LM2:KNZ[A]/KNM[A]*SQRT(MU),LM3:SQRT(MU)/WN[A],LM4:WN[A])\$
TIME= 151 MSEC.

(C51) MION:EV(MION,EVAL);
TIME= 5533 MSEC.

$$(D51)/R/ \quad \frac{-10 \cos(\alpha) \sin(\alpha) \sin(\beta) \frac{\text{KNM}^2}{A} + (-1 + 2 \sin^2(\alpha)) \frac{\text{KNM}^2}{A} \frac{\text{WN}}{A}}{2 \frac{\text{WN}^3}{A}}$$

Figure 4.3.1 (ix) Solution by Taylor series method

which certain operations are performed, see the appendix for details. In section 4.1 we mentioned that Taylor series in MACSYMA were put in a special "rational" form, which efficiently encodes polynomials; in line C2 we tell MACSYMA how we want the variables appearing in rational expressions ordered. (Rational expressions are polynomials in the last variable in the list; each coefficient of this polynomial is itself a polynomial in the second last variable, and so on.) In C3 we give the information on the ordering of the small parameters. We load up a file containing the expressions for the two parts of the ion term of the coupling coefficient (C5). The values of the frequencies and wave numbers, as defined at this point are displayed; as are MICONV and MIFLOW (E7 - E15). We load up the file containing the conductivity for a cold species (C16), and define an associated function for it (C20). Note that this definition involves taking a Taylor series, with the truncation level set at 2. It is only known this figure is sufficient for the truncation level after the whole calculation has been completed. In C21 we display the conductivity for each mode, and calculate and display VI, NI and VIT. Note that since the magnitude $KN[A]$ is of order DTA (see E10), it is necessary to reset the truncation level on SIGMAN[A] to 3 before doing the matrix operations. In this way we end up with sufficient significant terms in VI, NI and VIT. Having calculated these quantities, we can evaluate MICONV and MIFLOW (C31 and C32); note that before doing this we had to reset the truncation level of VI, NI and VIT to at least 3, because we wish to have MICONV and MIFLOW truncated at DTA^3 . The results are displayed (C34 and C35).

We notice that both C34 and C35 have lowest order terms which vary as $DTA * LM1$. But at the moment no cancellation is seen. In order to take the calculation further we must substitute in values for KN and WN as given by the resonance conditions (sec 3.4). In C37 we load up such values and display them E39 - E44.

Notice that we stored them as Taylor series with 3 significant terms. Before substituting these into MIFLOW and MICONV, we must reset their truncation level to 3 (C45). We then can re-evaluate the terms of the coupling coefficient (C46 and C47); TRIGRED is a function we have defined (in C36) to effect some trigonometric identities, (there is a MACSYMA function TRIGREDUCE, which has a similar effect, but it is rather more general than we require). At this stage we can add MIFLOW to MICONV to obtain MION (D48); note that the terms in DTA have cancelled and we are left with two terms in DTA12 and DTA13. Finally we substitute for DTA and the λ 's (C50 and C51), to obtain the answer for MION (D51).

In normal notation this expression for M_i looks like:

$$M_i \approx C (k_a c_s / \omega_a)^2 \times [-\cos 2\alpha - 5 i \sin 2\alpha \sin \beta \Omega_i / \omega_a] / 2 \quad (23)$$

where:

$$C = \frac{E_a E_b E_n^* \epsilon_0 \omega_{pi}^2 e}{k_a k_b k_n c_s^4 m_i} \quad (24)$$

As we have noted this result contains term of order δ^2 (the first part) and of order δ^3 (the second part). We also can see that the effect of the cancellations is to reduce the size of the coupling coefficient from ϵ_1 (see equations 11 and 12) to ϵ_1^2 .

If we carry out the calculation for the electron term to the same order we again observe the cancellations seen in section 4.2. So the sum of the flowcurrent and continuity terms which individually are of order $\mu \epsilon_1 \epsilon_2$ (i.e. δ^0), is of order $\epsilon_1 \epsilon_2$ (or δ^2). Adding this sum to the convective term, which also is of order $\epsilon_1 \epsilon_2$, we obtain a result which is of order $\epsilon_1^2 \epsilon_2^2$ (or δ^4). In this way we see that the biggest contribution to the electron term is from the pressure nonlinearity

(which is of order $\mu \epsilon_1^2 \epsilon_2^2$ or δ^2). So carrying out the whole calculation accurate to δ^3 we obtain:

$$M_e \simeq C (k_a c_s / \omega_a)^2 \times [-\mu \cos^2 \theta_a / 2 + \cos \theta_a \tan \alpha / \cos \beta] \quad (25)$$

Once again the terms in this expression are of order δ^2 and δ^3 respectively. These expressions will be discussed in section 4.5.

4.4 Coupling to Electrostatic Ion Cyclotron and Magnetosonic Waves

As before we will begin the analytic study of this interaction with a lowest order calculation, similar to the one presented at the beginning of section 4.3. The assumptions made about the pump in that case we will now make about the pump and the idler, since all are lower hybrid modes. So for these modes we will calculate the ion orbits assuming $B_0 \rightarrow 0$, and the electron orbits assuming $B_0 \rightarrow \infty$, and assume that $v_t \rightarrow 0$. Also we will use the same small parameters: $m_e/m_i \equiv \mu$, and $k_a c_s / \omega_a \equiv \epsilon_1$ and $\cos \theta_a \equiv \epsilon_2$; and say in addition that: $k_b c_s / \omega_b \simeq \epsilon_1$ and $\cos \theta_b \simeq \epsilon_2$. In that case the velocities and densities of modes a and b vary in the same way that they did for mode a in section 4.3 (equations 4.3.1 - 4.3.4). We will also assume that the resonant denominator $(\omega^2 - \Omega_i^2)$ that occurs in the ion conductivity for electrostatic ion cyclotron modes is of order ω^2 ; (remember that we cannot take ω too close to Ω_i , because the wave would be heavily electron cyclotron damped, see figure 3.3.1). Substituting into the coupling coefficient (equations 2.3.14 and 2.4.45) we find:

$$\text{electron convective} \sim \mu \epsilon_1^2 \epsilon_2^2 \quad (1)$$

$$\text{electron continuity} \sim \mu^2 \epsilon_1^3 \epsilon_2^3 \quad (2)$$

$$\text{electron flowcurrent} \sim \mu^2 \epsilon_1^3 \epsilon_2^3 \quad (3)$$

$$\text{electron pressure} \sim \mu^2 \epsilon_1^4 \epsilon_2^4 \quad (4)$$

$$\text{ion convective} \sim \epsilon_1^2 \quad (5)$$

$$\text{ion flowcurrent} \sim \epsilon_1^3 \quad (6)$$

Notice that the electron continuity and flowcurrent terms are again of the same order, which is necessary for the cancellations we saw numerically in section 4.2.

In order to derive the coupling coefficient for this case we will assume that the electron convective term is the dominant term. We saw that this was the case numerically (figures 4.2.3 and 4.2.4); and looking at equations 1 to 6, if we accept the fact that the electron continuity and flowcurrent terms very nearly cancel (see the same figures, we will examine the reason for this cancellation in section 4.5) then the largest contributions are going to come from the ion convective and electron convective terms. Comparing these two (equations 1 and 5) we see that their ratio (electron/ion) is about $\mu \epsilon_2^2$ or $\mu \cos^2 \theta_a$. But in section 3.4 we remarked that the resonance conditions forced us to take this ratio to be large, and so we are justified in including only the electron convective term, (i.e. the $(\mathbf{v} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{v}$ term in the electron momentum equation).

Since the dominant term is an electron term, it might seem that $B_0 \rightarrow \infty$ is a reasonable approximation, because $\Omega_e \gg \omega$ for all three modes. This assumption is justified for the case of coupling to magnetosonic waves. But note (equation 2.4.37) that such an assumption can only give a real answer for the normalized coupling coefficient as used in MACSYMA (figure 2.4.1); but we see from figure 4.2.3 (coupling to an electrostatic ion cyclotron wave), that the imaginary part of the electron term can be several times larger than the real part. This can be traced to the fact that since two of the modes (a and b) are at steep angles to the magnetic field, the electrons have an important component of their velocity in the $\mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}$ direction. For the modes we are considering this component of velocity is

usually smaller than the component parallel to the magnetic field (see E24 in figure 4.2.1). However the convective nonlinearity contains the dot product $\mathbf{v}_a \cdot \mathbf{k}_b$, and since \mathbf{k}_b is close to perpendicular to the magnetic field it will tend to pick out the $\mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}$ component of \mathbf{v}_a over the i_z component (see the coefficient of TERM1 CONVEC in C31 in figure 4.2.1). So it is here that we should include the $\mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}$ component of the electron velocity. If we do this and again assume that the electron orbits are correctly given by neglecting the pressure, we obtain the following coupling coefficient for electrostatic ion cyclotron and magnetosonic waves:

$$M = C [-\mu c_s^2 k_{az} k_{bz}/(\omega_a \omega_b) + i c_s^2 k_{ax} k_{by}/(\omega_a \Omega_i)]/2 \quad (7)$$

where C is defined in equation 4.3.24.

We based this derivation of M on somewhat crude reasoning. So it would be satisfying if we could apply the Taylor series method described in the last section to this case, and have the above result come out. However it appears to be difficult to find a simple ordering scheme, to make this happen. One scheme that we tried was to make $k_x \sim k \delta$ and $\omega \sim k c_s \delta$ for modes a and b , in addition to the magnetic field orderings (equations 4 and 5). Or in MACSYMA terms:

$$\text{MU} : 1 / \text{DTA}^2 \quad (8)$$

$$\text{WN}[A] : \text{KNM}[A] / \text{LM1}[A] / \text{DTA} \quad (9)$$

$$\text{KNZ}[A] : \text{KNM}[A] * \text{LM2}[A] * \text{DTA} \quad (10)$$

and similarly for mode B. When we carry out the calculation of the coupling coefficient we find that the coefficients of the resulting polynomial in DTA are of order DTA or higher. This makes it difficult to identify the largest terms in the answer, although the terms of equation 7 are present. Again the cancellation between flowcurrent and continuity terms is observed; so their sum is of order $\mu \epsilon_1^3 \epsilon_2^3$; (compare this with equations 2 and 3).

The problem appears to be that a more fine ordering scheme is required. This would be based on some quantity closer to unity than the δ we have been using. The effect of such an ordering scheme would be to separate the terms in the Taylor series in δ that we have derived using the coarser ordering. One consequence of this would be to make it necessary to set the truncation level higher than at present; so a more efficient ordering and truncating function than TAYLOR is required. Most of the expressions we deal with are polynomials or ratios of polynomials; so instead of using TAYLOR which works on quite general expressions, we can use the MACSYMA function WEIGHT which provides an efficient ordering of rational expressions. This should be the basis of further research.

4.5 *Discussion of Results*

One of the recurring phenomena we have encountered in calculating the growth rates is cancellations. Of these the most persistent has been the nearly total cancellation between the electron continuity and flowcurrent terms. The explanation for this cancellation is as follows. It is the flowcurrent nonlinearity ($n^{(1)} v^{(1)}$) that through its divergence provides the driving term for the second order continuity equation (2.4.12), and this gives rise to the continuity term in the second order current. Now, $\nabla \cdot (n^{(1)} v^{(1)})$ can be thought of as a creation of electron fluid which, if the rest of the electron fluid were stationary would lead to density fluctuations at the signal frequency and wave number. (Note that although the exact and linearized continuity equations obey conservation of particles, this is not the case for the second and higher order equations.) However for ion acoustic modes, and the other low frequency modes we couple to, pressure dominates over inertia, so the electron fluid is not stationary; on the contrary, it moves in such a way to nearly cancel out the density fluctuations. So the

response of the plasma to a continuity driving term is to produce currents that nearly cancel the flowcurrent term.

We now turn to the specific cases. For the ion acoustic problem we saw two other cancellations occurring while obtaining the expression for M_i and M_e (equations 4.4.11 and 4.4.12). Namely between the sum of the electron flowcurrent and continuity terms and the electron convective term, and between the two ion terms. These cancellations are more involved than the one discussed above, and are a result of the geometry of the interaction (specifically $k_b \sim k_n$, and $k_a \ll k_n$; see figure 3.4.2). Remember that to get these cancellations, we had to put in expressions for ω and k . A consequence of the cancellation in the ion terms is that, although all the modes are nearly unmagnetized so that the ion orbits are almost parallel to the wave vectors, the cancellation affects these component more than the $\mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}$ component of the velocities. So in addition to the real term in the equation 4.4.11 (which can be identified with the $B_0 \rightarrow 0$ limit) there is an imaginary term associated with the ellipticity of the ion orbits. The ratio of the real to imaginary parts of M_i is about $\omega_a / (5 \Omega_i)$ (ignoring the trigonometric factors) which is about unity for the plasmas we consider. Here we see the importance of adjusting the truncation level to get more than one term in the answer; for in the ordering scheme we choose for working with TAYLOR this ratio was of order δ^{-1} . Note that in order to take advantage of this term, B_0 and the k 's must not all lie in the same plane (i.e. β , see figure 3.4.2, must be non-zero).

As we have noted the various cancellations that take place when calculating M_e end up making the pressure term the most important one. The ratio of the first to second terms in the expression for M_e (equation 4.4.12) is (again ignoring trigonometric factors) $\mu \cos \theta_a$, which is only less than unity if $\cos \theta_a < \mu^{-1}$; but

in that case the whole electron term is small, and so we are safe in discarding the second term in equation 4.4.12, to obtain:

$$M_e \approx -C \mu/2 (k_{az} c_s/\omega_a)^2 \quad (1)$$

Comparing the ion and electron terms in the coupling coefficient we see that their ratio is approximately $\mu \cos^2 \theta_a$ (which is of order δ^0 in the ordering scheme we chose for MACSYMA). Now we saw in section 3.4 that if we wished the pump to be a mode, the resonance conditions restricted us to where $\mu \cos^2 \theta_a \ll 1$. In other words we had to choose the wave vector of the pump so close to perpendicular to the magnetic field that the electrons, which are virtually constrained to moving along the magnetic field, have such a small velocity that they no longer contribute significantly to the coupling. So we may say $M \approx M_i$ with M_i given by equation 4.4.11.

For coupling to electrostatic ion cyclotron and magnetosonic waves we saw that the largest ion term was the convective, and that after the cancellation between electron flowcurrent and continuity terms, the largest electron term was also the convective. Of these the electron term was found to dominate numerically. Comparing the two terms using our ordering scheme from section 4.3 (equations 4.3.13 and 4.3.17) we see that their ratio (electron/ion) is of the order of $\mu \epsilon_1^2$ or $\mu \cos^2 \theta_{a_i}$; and as we saw in section 3.4 the resonance conditions force us to take $\cos^2 \theta_a \gg \mu^{-1}$; from which we see that indeed the electron term will be the largest. The coupling coefficient we calculated on the basis of this information is given in equation 4.3.19. This time we can identify the real part of the expression as being due to the z directed velocity component only, and the imaginary part as being due to the $E \times B$ corrections to the velocity. Comparing these two parts we find that their ratio (imaginary/real) is:

$$\sin \psi \omega_{bi}^2 / (\Omega_i \omega_b) \quad (2)$$

where ψ is defined in figure 3.4.4(a). It is interesting to examine how the factor of $\sin \psi$ enters. If we consider the dot product $\mathbf{v}_a \cdot \mathbf{k}_b$, that appears in the convective term, then \mathbf{v}_a is going to have two main components: one along B_0 and one along the y axis (the $\mathbf{E} \times \mathbf{B}$ direction, don't forget that \mathbf{k}_a lies in the x, z plane). Since k_{bz} is small taking the dot product will tend to suppress the z component of \mathbf{v}_a . However by allowing \mathbf{k}_b to have a large y component we can pick out nearly all of the y component of \mathbf{a} 's velocity; but we see from figure 3.4.4(a) that this is equivalent to allowing the angle ψ to approach $\pi/2$. In the cases we consider ω_b is a few times ω_{bi} , whereas Ω_i is considerably smaller, and so the ratio in (2) is larger than one so long as $\sin \psi \sim 1$. As was pointed out in section 3.4 it is possible to achieve this condition for coupling to electrostatic ion cyclotron waves, but not for coupling to magnetosonic waves. So although the nature of the interacting waves (\mathbf{a} and \mathbf{b}) is very similar for coupling to both these low frequency waves, the nature of the low frequency wave affects the geometry of the interaction, and so changes the principle mechanism for the interaction.

4.6 Calculation of Growth Rates and Thresholds

The step from our coupling coefficient (M) to a growth rate was given in equation 2.3.20. The only additional work required is the calculation of wave energy densities for the idler and signal of each interaction. The formula for energy density is (equation 3.1.8):

$$W = W_e \omega \partial K / \partial \omega \quad (1)$$

where W_e (the electric energy density) is given by:

$$W_e \equiv \frac{1}{4} \epsilon_0 |E|^2 \quad (2)$$

and K is the electrostatic dispersion relation defined in equation 3.1.15. For each

mode we can make the same approximations we made to get its approximate dispersion relation. Then it is easy to show that for lower hybrid modes:

$$W = 2 W_e \quad (3)$$

while for ion acoustic waves

$$W = 2 \omega_{pi}^2 / \omega^2 W_e \quad (4)$$

for magnetosonic waves

$$W = 2 \omega_{Li}^2 / \omega^2 \xi^2 W_e \quad (5)$$

and for electrostatic ion cyclotron waves:

$$W = 2 \omega_{pi}^2 \omega^2 / (\omega^2 - \Omega_i^2)^2 \xi^2 W_e \quad (6)$$

Substituting these expressions into 2.3.20 and using the expressions for M given in equation 4.4.11, we find that for coupling to ion acoustic waves the growth rate γ_0 is given by:

$$\frac{\gamma_0}{\omega_n} \approx \frac{v_{ai}}{4 (\omega_a / k_a)} \left| \cos 2\alpha + i \frac{\Omega_i}{\omega_a} 5 \sin 2\alpha \sin \beta \right| \quad (7)$$

where:

$$v_{ai} \equiv e |E_a| / (m_i \omega_a) \quad (8)$$

For coupling to electrostatic ion cyclotron waves we use equation 4.3.19 to give M . Then γ_0 is given by:

$$\frac{\gamma_0}{|\omega_b \omega_n|^{1/2}} \approx \frac{\omega_n^2 - \Omega_i^2}{4 v_{te} k_{n\perp} \omega_n c_s} \left| v_{ae\parallel} + i \frac{\omega_{pe}}{\omega_a} \sin \psi v_{ae\perp} \right| \quad (9)$$

where:

$$v_{ae\parallel} \equiv e |E_{ax}| / (m_e \omega_a) \quad (10)$$

$$v_{ae\perp} \equiv |E_a| / B_0 \quad (11)$$

We have already compared the terms appearing in equation 9 in section 4.5. The second term appearing here is similar the zero k pump result of Kindel, Okuda and

Dawson [K11].

Lastly for coupling to magnetosonic waves we also use equation 4.3.19 for M , but we omit the second term, for the reasons given in the last section. Then we find:

$$\gamma_0 / |\omega_b \omega_n|^{1/2} \approx 1/4 v_{ae11} / v_{te} \quad (12)$$

We can now use these formulae for γ_0 to find typical threshold fields for the interaction. The threshold condition was given in equation 2.3.21. We will take as an example a typical tokamak type hydrogen plasma, with the following parameters:

$$B_0 = 30 \text{ kG (3 T)}$$

$$n_0 = 2 \times 10^{13} \text{ cm}^{-3} \quad (2 \times 10^{19} \text{ m}^{-3})$$

$$T_e = 1 \text{ keV}$$

Then if T_e/T_i is about five, we can expect the relative damping of the low frequency waves to be about 0.1, and of the lower hybrid waves to be of the order of 10^{-5} (see reference Te1). The threshold fields then come out to be approximately as follows:

Coupling to:	Threshold field (V/cm)
Ion acoustic	10^6
Electrostatic ion cyclotron	10^2
Magnetosonic	10^3

These figures should only be regarded as rough guides. Note the high threshold for coupling to ion acoustic waves, as compared to the other interactions. This is because this interaction excites *two* relatively highly damped modes, whereas with the others the idler is very lightly damped.

CHAPTER FIVE
APPLICATION TO INHOMOGENEOUS PLASMAS

5.1 The Briggs Parker Result

All of the work described in the previous chapters strictly applies only to homogeneous plasmas. However there are some cases where, if the density gradient is weak enough, it can be applied to inhomogeneous plasmas as well. Another restriction on the ground covered in the last chapters is that the pump field has only a single wave number. Again, in some circumstances, the theory will be applicable to cases where the pump is of finite spatial extent, and so contains a spectrum of wave numbers. Before tackling these cases, it is important to have some understanding of the plasma in the linear regime, under these conditions. Of particular interest here is the excitation of lower hybrid waves, in the interior of an inhomogeneous plasma, where the exciting structures are restricted to the walls of the confining vessel, (a necessary condition for any potential fusion device). These waves will act as our pump when we consider the nonlinear problem. The course taken here closely follows that of Briggs and Parker. The reader is referred to their paper [Br1] for a fuller discussion.

The case we restrict ourselves to is that in which ∇n is constant and perpendicular to B_0 (a constant). This case can be considered as a planar analogue of a tokamak. As usual we will take B_0 to be in the z direction. We will choose the density gradient to be in the x direction so that $\nabla n_0 = n_0' i_x$. The general layout is shown in figure 1(a).

We will assume that a waveguide which terminates at the wall of the confining vessel acts as a source of fields, and examine how lower hybrid waves are

(a)

(b)

Figure 5.1.1 Propagation in an inhomogeneous Plasma. (a) general layout and ray path (b) segment of ray at $x \approx x_0$

excited in the interior of the plasma. Since lower hybrid waves are adequately described by a cold electrostatic plasma dispersion relation, we shall assume that the plasma is cold and describable in the electrostatic limit, while dealing with linear propagation. This approximation considerably simplifies the linear picture, because of the simple dispersion relation for cold electrostatic waves: $\omega = \omega(k, n_0)$. The solution of the problem with temperature effects included is still not fully worked out. It seems that linear wave conversion processes take place in such a case [Si1].

We wish to have a description of wave phenomena in an inhomogeneous plasma. However the use of Fourier transforms to split the fields into independent modes only works in the directions of homogeneity (i.e. y and z). For any k_y and k_z there will in general be a complicated functional dependence of the fields on the x coordinate. For the analysis to be tractible we will make the approximation that the density gradient is in some sense *weak*. Then solution of the linear problem is possible using WKB techniques. In such a theory the density gradient is assumed weak enough that at any point in the plasma a k_x can be identified. It is found that this k_x satisfies the linear dispersion relation for a homogeneous plasma, whose density is the same as the local plasma density. Then if a potential $\Phi_0(z)$ is set up at the walls of the system ($x = 0$) and if $\partial/\partial y = 0$, the potential in the interior of the plasma is given by the solution of:

$$\frac{\partial}{\partial x} K_{\perp} \frac{\partial}{\partial x} \Phi(x, k_z) - k_z^2 K_{\parallel} \Phi(x, k_z) = 0 \quad (1)$$

For this the WKB solution is:

$$\Phi(x, k_z) = \Phi_0(k_z) \left[\frac{K_{\parallel}(0) K_{\perp}(0)}{K_{\parallel}(x) K_{\perp}(x)} \right]^{1/4} \exp(i \int^x k_x dx) \quad (2)$$

where $\Phi_0(k_z)$ is the Fourier transform of $\Phi_0(z)$ and:

$$k_x(x) = |k_z| [-K_{||}(x)/K_{\perp}(x)]^{1/2} \quad (3)$$

K_{\perp} and $K_{||}$ are the x,x and z,z components of the dielectric tensor \mathbf{K} (equation 2.1.10). In our case we take $v_t = 0$, and for the waves we are considering $\Omega_e^2 \gg \omega^2 \gg \Omega_i^2$. For tokamak type plasmas we can assume that $\Omega_e^2 \gg \omega_{pe}^2$. Then:

$$K_{\perp} \approx 1 - \omega_{pi}^2/\omega^2 \quad (4)$$

$$K_{||} = 1 - \omega_{pe}^2/\omega^2 \quad (5)$$

(Remember that the plasma frequencies are a function of density and so of x). Note that with these values for K_{\perp} and $K_{||}$ there will be a small region of evanescence (k_x pure imaginary) in the low density part of the plasma when ω exceeds the local electron plasma frequency and $K_{||} > 0$. Normally we are interested in frequencies low enough that this layer of decaying fields is extremely thin. We shall assume here that there is no reflection of energy by this layer.

An important consequence of the cold plasma model assumed is that \mathbf{K} is independent of k , so from equation 3 we see that at any x , k_x is proportional to k_z . Then from equation 2 we see that, $\Phi(x, k_z)$ is phase shifted from $\Phi_0(k_z)$ by an amount proportional to k_z . In other words the field patterns at x are a translated version of those at $x = 0$. It is found [Br1] that the field patterns follow a trajectory:

$$z = \int^x (-K_{||}/K_{\perp})^{1/2} dx \quad (6)$$

For \mathbf{K} as given by equations 4 and 5, this path is shown in figure 1(a). Notice the greatly distorted scale of the figure. The ray path in fact spends most of the time travelling very nearly parallel ($\sim \mu^{-1/2}$) to B_0 (see figure 1(b)). For this reason the width of the ray in the x direction becomes very small; if the width of the source (at $x = 0$) is w_0 , then the width, w , in the interior is of order $w_0/\mu^{1/2}$; so taking 5 cm as being a reasonable maximum value for w_0 , we find $w \sim 1$ mm. The electric fields in this ray are perpendicular to the direction of the ray and the group velocity is parallel to it.

The ray stops penetrating and travels only along the magnetic field when it reaches the *lower hybrid resonance layer*, $x = x_0$, at which point $\omega = \omega_{lh} \approx \omega_{Dl}$. The cold plasma assumption breaks down here because infinite fields are predicted, and an exact description of the fate of the ray would have to include temperature effects. Lastly we note that equation 2 predicts amplification of the fields. The amplification factor for the magnitude of the electric field, assuming no region of evanescence (not strictly true as we have seen), is about:

$$\mu^{1/4} x'^{1/4} (1 - x')^{-3/4} \quad (6)$$

where $x' \equiv x/x_0$ and $\mu \equiv m_i/m_e$. For a hydrogen plasma, at $x' = 1/2$, ($\omega = 2^{1/2} \omega_{Dl}$), this factor is approximately 10.

5.2 Criterion for Growth with a Finite Pump

We now try to apply the results of chapter 4 to the plasma described in the last section. A comprehensive analysis of this problem is obviously very complex, and we shall find it necessary to make some drastic assumptions, in order to gain any insight of the problem.

We first of all will assume that the growth of waves in the ray is the same as if the pump were uniform. We can only make this assumption if the several wavelengths of the excited waves can fit into the pump region. The wavelengths of the waves we are exciting are around 1 - 10 mm, with the plasma parameters given in section 4.6. If we take the waveguide width, w_0 in figure 5.1.1 to be 5 cm (as an upper limit), then the width of the ray of figure 5.1.1 in the interior of the plasma is about 1 mm (see section 5.1). So before we can contemplate exciting any waves we have to find some means by which a broader pump region is excited. A possible scheme for doing just this is shown in figure 1, in which a phased

(a)

(b)

Figure 5.2.1 Excitation with many waveguides.
 (a) ray paths, (b) density profile

waveguide array is set up at the walls of the confining vessel.

The second assumption we will make, is that the density gradient is weak enough that the nonlinear interaction does not feel its effects. This requires that the interaction is localized in a region small compared with the density scale length. It also requires that unstable pulses do not move so far that they are in a region where the wave number matching condition (equation 3.4.1) fails and there is a resultant δk (equation 2.3.9) large enough to "switch off" the interaction. We will examine this condition more fully in a while.

With these assumptions we form the following picture. An unstable pulse originating from noise begins to grow within the pump region. The behaviour of such a pulse in a uniform pump is well understood (see reference Be3). It is found that the pulse is confined to a line between two points, $v_{ob} t$ and $v_{on} t$ from the point where the pulse started. (Note that these are points moving with the group velocities of the idler and signal.) The centre of the pulse grows (temporally) at γ_0 , in the absence of damping. After a while the edges of the pulse will move outside the pump region. We will assume however that the rest of the pulse grows as if the pump were uniform. Some time later the centre on the pulse, which travels at $\frac{1}{2}(v_{ob} + v_{on})$, exits the pump region. We will arbitrarily call the interaction a *strong* one if this part of the pulse has e -folded several times at this point, or:

$$l \equiv \frac{1}{2}(v_{ob} + v_{on}) \cdot i_n / \gamma_0 \ll w \quad (1)$$

where we have defined a "growth length" l ; w is the width of the pump region and i_n is its normal vector (see figure 5.1.1).

We will now focus on the excitation of electrostatic ion cyclotron modes, since this interaction has the lowest threshold, and seems the best candidate for plasma heating. Suppose we take 1 kV/cm as being the maximum reasonable field we

can excite from the waveguide source; then assuming amplification by a factor of 10, as the ray penetrates the plasma, we have fields on the order of 10 kV/cm inside the plasma. This field is considerably above the threshold given in section 4.6, so the growth rate for the waves is given by γ_0 , as was assumed in (1). Substituting the plasma parameters given in section 4.6 into equation 4.6.9, we find that $\gamma_0 \sim 0.1 |\omega_b \omega_n|^{1/2}$. Although this growth rate is an insensitive function of the particular geometry of the interaction, l is strongly dependent on the geometry. This is because $v_{\sigma b} \gg v_{\sigma n}$ (see equations 3.3.1 and 3.3.3); now the direction of $v_{\sigma b}$ changes as k_b is changed, and the size of l will depend on how close $v_{\sigma a}$ and $v_{\sigma b}$ are to being parallel, (i_n is perpendicular to $v_{\sigma a}$). We can distinguish two cases: firstly $k_a \neq 0$, in which case the interaction belongs to the class given in figure 3.4.3(b) for reasons given in section 3.4, and in this case there is a sizable component of $v_{\sigma b}$ in the i_n direction; secondly with $k_a \approx 0$ when we can choose k_a and k_b to be nearly parallel, in which case $v_{\sigma b}$ and i_n are nearly perpendicular. We find that in the first case $l \sim 25$ mm, and that in the second $l \sim 1$ mm; and so if the width of the ray produced by a single waveguide is 1 mm (as was assumed in section 5.1), we see that for excitation from many waveguides, unstable pulses will e -fold as many times as there are waveguides, for the zero k_a case.

If we wish to utilize the zero k_a interaction we will note that $k_b = k_n$, and because of the restrictions placed on the electrostatic ion cyclotron mode (mode n , see section 3.3), θ_b and θ_n have to lie in the range $83^\circ - 86^\circ$. In that case ω_a would have to be about 4 times the local lower hybrid frequency. In figure 1 we have assumed a somewhat more realistic density gradient than depicted in figure 5.1.1; in this case we would probably try to adjust the pump frequency, such that the ray penetrated right into the homogeneous region, where $\omega_{ni} \sim 1/4 \omega_a$.

For interactions occurring in the homogeneous parts of the plasma, we are obviously not concerned with problems of k matching. However even with the arrangement shown in figure 1, electrostatic ion cyclotron waves will be excited in the inhomogeneous region, at say half the peak density. (The growth of these waves will be similar to those in the homogeneous region, since the dependence goes at worst as $\cos \theta_a$, see equation 4.6.9.) These interactions do experience a "detuning" in k_x as the pulse travels through the density gradient; there is no mismatch in k_y or k_z , because these are the directions of homogeneity. (The reason for this detuning in k_x is simply that the dispersion relation for lower hybrid waves is a function of density; so for a fixed frequency, k must change as the density is changed.) This phenomenon only becomes important when the k_x mismatch, δk_x , is of the order of the spatial growth rate in the x direction. We can use this to give a scale length in the x direction, l_k , for this detuning. We find:

$$l_k \sim L \gamma_0 / \omega_a \quad (2)$$

where L is the density gradient scale length. Using the value of γ_0 given earlier, we find that with waveguide fields of 1 kV/cm, l_k is about 0.01 times L . This clearly will limit the excitation of electrostatic ion cyclotron waves in the inhomogeneous region. So we can expect the main excitation of low frequency waves to take place in the centre of the plasma, where as we have found considerable amplification of noise is possible.

CHAPTER SIX
CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

In chapter 3 we saw that nonlinear wave - wave interactions were possible, that involved a lower hybrid pump coupling to ion acoustic, electrostatic ion cyclotron or magnetosonic waves. In chapter 4 we used the coupling of modes formalism given in chapter 2 to derive analytic expressions for the growth rates of the excited waves. These expressions are fairly general, and in particular they allow a large variation in the angles of propagation of the interacting waves. For this reason we were able to apply the results to an inhomogeneous plasma (chapter 5). We considered the case where the pump was excited by several waveguides. In that case, with waveguide fields of about 1 kV/cm it appears to be possible to amplify several times any noise that exists near the frequencies and wave numbers of electrostatic ion cyclotron waves. Such a scheme might well result in significant heating of the ions.

The main area where the work presented in this thesis could be extended is in its application to the inhomogeneous plasma, with a spatially finite pump. It would be useful to have a more exact knowledge of the behaviour of the unstable pulse in an inhomogeneous plasma. Rosenbluth gives a WKB analysis for the one dimensional case [Ro1], but the two dimensional solution is unknown. More exact calculations of the degree of plasma heating by the method suggested with a given noise level are needed. Finally other schemes for exciting these nonlinear interactions should be considered. One possibility might be to drive the plasma by *two* pumps, instead of the one pump interaction considered here. Other means of exciting the lower hybrid waves should be investigated; Puri [Pu1] has done some work on this.

Since extensive use was made of symbolic computation on MACSYMA for the work described here, an evaluation of its performance is in order. Firstly, it should be noted that several months of effort were required to become familiar enough with the system, to solve the problems presented here. It seems that although individual functions in MACSYMA are easily mastered, the use of many commands to solve a large problem requires some knowledge of the rather subtle issues of evaluation that occur in symbolic computation. For this reason an inexperienced user would have to be prepared to invest a large amount of time to solve a problem of any complexity; in which case it is probably only worth the effort if there is little chance of doing it any other way. Of the work done on MACSYMA described here, probably only that involving Taylor series (see figure 4.3.1) falls into that category. The rest, which consisted mainly of the numerical calculations (see figure 4.2.1), is justifiable in this case partly because MACSYMA displays the intermediate results in a way that is similar to the way one might write them, and that made the evaluation of the computer outputs particularly easy. The situation is probably somewhat different with users who have already had some experience with MACSYMA. In this case the investment of time and effort in starting a new problem is much less, results are obtained more quickly, and it would probably be worth using MACSYMA for a variety of smaller problems, which although they might be solved by hand, can now be done faster using MACSYMA. The other positive aspect of working with a symbolic computation system is this: the initial setting up of the problem, and its solution might require considerable time; however the solution of the same problem with slight modifications can probably be done in a fraction of the time. So for instance if we wanted an additional term in the answer for the coupling coefficient for the interaction involving ion acoustic waves (equation 4.3.23), we would merely have to re-enter the original commands, with the truncation levels incremented by

one, and assuming storage capacity is not exceeded, we would obtain the new answer.

Future work that could be **done** on MACSYMA, that would be relevant to our work, would be the utilization of WEIGHT, (which assigns weights to variables to govern the truncation of expressions). This is potentially much more efficient than TAYLOR for many problems, and also gives the user more flexibility in deciding how expressions should be truncated.

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APPENDIX

MACSYMA FUNCTIONS AND SWITCHES

Functions

ATAN(<i>expr</i>)	arctangent of <i>expr</i>
BLOCK(...)	executes its arguments (separated by commas)
COSH(<i>expr</i>)	hyperbolic cosine of <i>expr</i>
DIFF(<i>expr</i> , <i>x</i>)	differentiate <i>expr</i> with respect to <i>x</i>
DISPLAY(...)	displays the values of its arguments
DISPTERMS(<i>expr</i>)	displays the terms in <i>expr</i>
EV(<i>expr</i> ,...)	evaluate <i>expr</i> in the context of the following arguments
EXPAND(<i>expr</i>)	expand <i>expr</i>
INTEGRATE(<i>expr</i> , <i>x</i>)	integrate <i>expr</i> with respect to <i>x</i>
KILL(...)	removes its arguments from the system, and frees the storage they used
LOADFILE(<i>fspec</i>)	loads in a file given by <i>fspec</i>
MATRIXMAP(<i>fn</i> , <i>mx</i>)	maps the function <i>fn</i> onto the elements of the matrix <i>mx</i>
RATDISREP(<i>expr</i>)	converts <i>expr</i> into "general representation"
RATSIMP(<i>expr</i>)	"rationally" simplifies <i>expr</i> , result is a ratio of two polynomials
RATVARS(...)	governs the ordering of variables in rational expressions
SOLVE(<i>eq</i> , <i>x</i>)	solve <i>eq</i> for <i>x</i>
SQRT(<i>expr</i>)	square root of <i>expr</i>
SUBST([<i>eq1</i> , <i>eq2</i> ,...], <i>expr</i>)	substitute equations <i>eq1</i> , <i>eq2</i> ,... into <i>expr</i>
TAYLOR(<i>expr</i> , <i>x</i> , <i>pt</i> , <i>pow</i>)	take Taylor series of <i>expr</i> in <i>x</i> about <i>pt</i> , truncating at <i>pow</i>
TRIGREDUCE(<i>expr</i>)	express powers of trigonometric functions occurring in <i>expr</i> as trigonometric functions of multiple arguments
WEIGHT(<i>x</i> , <i>wt</i>)	gives <i>x</i> the weight <i>wt</i> ; used to govern the truncation of extended rational expressions

Switches

DOALLMXOPS	if TRUE causes all matrix operations to be carried out
DOTASSOC	if TRUE causes (A.B).C to simplify to A.(B.C)
DOTSCRULES	if TRUE causes certain rules for expressions containing scalars and matrices to be effected
EVAL	as an argument to EV causes an additional evaluation
EZGCDSWITCH	if FALSE stops the application of the "EZGCD" algorithm for the taking of greatest common divisors
FLOAT	if TRUE causes non-integral numbers to be converted to floating point
LINEL	sets length of line for MACSYMA output
NOLABELS	if TRUE stops the labelled lines (C1, D1, E2 etc.) from being saved
NUMER	if TRUE causes certain functions (e.g. the trigonometric functions) with numeric arguments to evaluate to a floating point number
POWERDISP	if TRUE causes polynomials to be displayed as powerseries
RATMX	if TRUE matrix operations will be done in rational representation
TIME	if TRUE prints the time of each computation